
Studiengang Digitales Datenmanagement (DDM)
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Masterarbeit

Does size matter? Quality assessment of the size property in research data repositories

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Table of Contents

List of Figures	3
List of Abbreviations.....	4
1. Introduction	7
1.1. Research Context	7
1.2. Problem Statement	7
1.3. Research Question	8
2. Literature review	10
2.1. Research Data Repositories	10
2.2. Registries for Repositories	11
2.2.1. re3data	11
2.2.2. FAIRsharing.....	13
2.2.3. OpenDOAR	14
2.2.4. Other Initiatives.....	15
2.3. Data Size/Repository Size.....	16
2.4. Metadata Quality	18
2.5. The Bibliographic World: Resource Description and Access (RDA)	20
3. Methodology.....	23
3.1. Data Analysis of re3data	23
3.1.1. Property Selection.....	23
3.1.2. Data Extraction.....	23
3.1.3. Data Processing	23
3.1.4. Data Typing.....	24
3.1.5. Data Analysis	25
3.2. Case Study of Sample Repositories	29
4. Results	31
4.1. Data Analysis	31
4.1.1. Univariate	31
4.1.2. Multivariate and Time	53
4.2. Case Study	56
5. Discussion.....	57
5.1. Q1.....	57
5.2. Q2.....	59
5.3. Q3.1.....	61

5.4. Q3.2	64
6. Conclusion	67
References.....	71
Affidavit	80
Appendices	
A Case Study of Repositories.....	I - XXIII
B Data Management Plan	1 - 9
C Overview over Research Data and Code.....	1

List of Figures

Figure 1: re3data registration workflow	11
Figure 2: Aspects of a Research Data Repository with the corresponding icons used in re3data.org .	12
Figure 3: IFLA LRM-E4-A2 Extent.....	21
Figure 4: repositoryIdentifier	31
Figure 5: description.....	32
Figure 6: size.....	33
Figure 7: size_number with no size_unit	33
Figure 8: size_unit per repository	34
Figure 9: size_unit_type	35
Figure 10: size_unit_discipline	36
Figure 11: size_unit_content.....	37
Figure 12: size_unit_content_other.....	38
Figure 13: size_non_unit_type.....	39
Figure 14: size_quality.....	40
Figure 15: size_quality one error	40
Figure 16: size_quality two errors.....	41
Figure 17: size_quality three errors	41
Figure 18: updated_quality	42
Figure 19: providerType	43
Figure 20: databaseAccessType	44
Figure 21: dataUploadType	45
Figure 22: softwareName.....	46
Figure 23: apiType	47
Figure 24: pidSystem	48
Figure 25: enhancedPublication.....	49
Figure 26: certificate	50
Figure 27: metadataStandardName.....	51
Figure 28: remarks	52
Figure 29: size_unit_discipline and size_unit_content	53
Figure 30: Implausibilities between updated_corrected and lastUpdate	54
Figure 31: Debatables between updated_corrected and entryDate	54
Figure 32: updated_corrected boxplot	55
Figure 33: updated_corrected table	55
Figure 34: dif_update_last boxpot	56
Figure 35: dif_update_last table	56

List of Abbreviations

API Application Programming Interface
ARK Archival Resource Key
BUIR Bilkent University Institutional Repository
CC0 Creative Commons License Zero
CKAN Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
Clarín Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
COAR Confederation of Open Access Repositories
COREF Community Driven Open Reference for Research Data Repositories
CTS CoreTrustSeal
CURL Consortium of University Research Libraries
DFG German Research Foundation
DINI Deutsche Initiative für Netzwerkinformation
DOI Digital Object Identifier
DORA San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment
DRAWG Research Data Alliance Working Group on Data Granularity
DSA Data Seal of Approval
ELIXIR European life-sciences Infrastructure for biological Information
ELN Electronic Lab Notebook
FAIR Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FDO FAIR Digital Objects
FTP File Transfer Protocol
GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences
GUI Graphical User Interface
hdl Handle System Identifier
ICSD Inorganic Crystal Structure Database
IFLA LRM International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions Library Reference Model
ISO International Organization for Standardization
Jisc Joint Information Systems Committee
JSC Jülich Supercomputing Centre
KIT Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
MIME Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions
NCBI National Center for Biotechnology Information Gene Expression Omnibus
NetCDF Network Common Data Form
NFDI4Ing National Research Data Infrastructure for Engineering Sciences
NIH National Institutes of Health
OAI-PMH Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OpenDAP Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol
OpenDOAR Directory of Open Access Repositories
ORCID Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OSI Open Society Institute
PID Persistent Identifier
PURL Persistent Uniform Resource Locator
RatSWD German Data Forum
RDA Resource Description and Access, Research Data Alliance
RDR research data repository
re3data registry of research data repositories
REST Representational State Transfer
ROAR Registry of Open Access Repositories
ROR Research Organization Registry
SI International System of Units
SOAP Simple Object Access Protocol

SPARC Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition
SPARQL SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SWORD Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit
URN Uniform Resource Name
WDS ISC World Data System

The Count

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(ASCII Art, 2023)

*I count the spiders on the wall ...
I count the cobwebs in the hall ...
I count the candles on the shelf ...
When I'm alone, I count myself!*

(Moss, 1973)

1. Introduction

1.1. Research Context

In the last decade, an increasing amount of research has been carried out investigating the vital role of repositories within the area of research data management. Despite the challenges repositories face in dealing with an ever-evolving publishing landscape (Khan et al., 2021, p. 27), generalist repositories are, for example, a central resource for publishing research datasets (Assante et al., 2016, p. 19). In addition, a trend can be identified that seems committed to the principles of Open Science, which can be seen in massive EU activities such as Horizon Europe and the European Open Science Cloud (European Commission, 2022b, pp. 37; 45). Increasing demands also accompany this on the infrastructure, which can culminate, for instance, in the TRUST principles (Lin et al., 2020) for digital repositories. In this problem area, in addition to repositories as core structures, there are meta-services such as re3data (registry of research data repositories), which are recommended for researchers to fulfil discovery functions (Network of the National Library of Medicine, 2022). At the same time, they can be seen as anchor points where funder or research programme requirements can be reflected (Vieira, 2023).

Strongly linked to the research infrastructure landscape are questions of overarching standardisation or at least data exchange and subsequent concepts of quality assurance, which can be seen in heavily used frameworks such as the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016). Various international stakeholders support these concepts, first and foremost by committed researchers themselves. Networks, such as RDA (Research Data Alliance, 2016), are a place where such concepts and standards are discussed, developed in groups and disseminated to the user communities. Quality and quality assurance play a central role in all of the above. It can be applied at different levels, e.g. to the data or to the services themselves. How complex quality can be for the repository sector alone can be seen in the formation of abstract frameworks to describe quality assurance measures (Kindling, 2022, p. 178 f.). This is especially true for Open Data, where the issuing organisation must critically examine its own data lifecycle and its impact on quality (Abella et al., 2019, p. 296). Measuring this scientific output has always played an essential role in research and for its actors, e.g. for funders or researchers. The methods and metrics required for this and their significance are continuously discussed in the scientific community, and a critical questioning of the “belief in numbers” can be seen, for example, in the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) (American Society for Cell Biology (ASCB), 2012).

1.2. Problem Statement

A fraction of research in data management regards the importance of metadata of research data repositories and how it is provided via registries. Unfortunately, only some researchers have treated

in detail how this metadata of repositories is created and maintained. Metadata quality is of utmost importance when it comes to the usefulness and usability of resource collections such as repositories and research data alike, which could also influence each other. Thus, low-quality metadata can lead to a negative impact. Despite investing considerable personnel resources in optimisation, errors and inconsistencies occur, especially when leaving highly standardized and conform areas such as bibliographic databases (Zeng & Qin, 2016, p. 317).

Traditionally, the problem of cataloguing quality has been assessed with the help of quantitative studies, e.g. with a model for the holdings of the British Library (MacEwan & Young, 2004). These studies were mostly limited to classic bibliographic material such as books and articles. This method is particularly useful in measuring the attributes of cataloguing quality in relation to information retrieval but seems too advanced for pioneer work in indexing repositories. The question of a trust model for editing this metadata remains and is significant to ensure sustainability. The different roles of editors, researchers and repository operators are of interest in answering this question.

The concept of a repository's size, modelled in the well-established registry re3data, offers substance for research in the area of metadata. The author believes the effort to investigate this peculiar property is worthwhile. This has been shown recently by the interest of the Research Data Alliance Working Group on Data Granularity (DRAWG) in the matter (RDA Data Granularity Working Group, 2021). Granularity or size in the field of information science is a rather vague concept (Hider, 2018, p. 20) if you leave out classical file size, which has the highest comparative value with unit measurement in metrology. Unlike physical units, something is counted that is not an exact quantity because units like datasets are not defined strictly and may never be fully defined. So it seems to be less about precision, and yet there is evidently a need to count data and present size. This is currently fulfilled in various ways, even if the results (specifically the units) are not free of contradictions and can easily change their scale; just imagine packing 3000 files into a single file. Furthermore, it is particularly challenging when one leaves the level of individual data and goes to the level of a data repository. Besides adding up the items, questions arise about the meaning of a repository and the measurability of research. Subsequently, indexing rules are necessary to guarantee quality control for this attribute and in concordance with all other size-related properties.

1.3. Research Question

This thesis attempts to fill this gap by analysing the size property of the metadata of a repository in re3data in the form of a data analysis of re3data's records combined with a case study. The author will thereupon refine the cataloguing model for addressing the challenges of indexing the size property of a repository in questions such as: How does an editor recognise the property at a repositories website? What are appropriate sources? What measures are needed for consistent data?

Rapidly changing properties, which rely on data in a repository and not on the repository itself, have to be dealt with differently than properties such as start date. With the refined model, which considers all existing records and concrete detection problems at a repository's website, size information should be captured more precisely and coherently. Therefore, evaluating a collection grown for ten years and trying to improve quality control seems reasonable. Size is one of re3data's properties with the most unstructured values (mixed content: numerical, strings, no controlled vocabulary), stands largely on its own and offers certain indexing challenges. That is why the author sees excellent potential for evaluation. The reader has to bear in mind that only one property of a complex schema from one registry to describe a repository will be investigated. Deeper relations and dependencies to other properties can only be touched lightly; transfers are, of course, possible and insightful regarding quality factors. Limiting this research to only one property means that it will not be possible to draw widespread conclusions but rather to explore some features of a repository thoroughly. The investigation also reveals singular information why size information is not available for some repositories and gives insights into improving the schema and the existing values. In order to address the mentioned issues, the following research questions are identified:

Q1: For what semantic concepts is the size property of repositories being used?

Q2: What kind of quality factors can be detected when assessing the size property in a registry for research data repositories (re3data)?

Q3: Which automated (Q3.1) and intellectual (Q3.2) measures can improve the quality of the size property?

On the one hand, the thesis seeks to lay the groundwork and evaluate future automation options and, on the other hand, to offer a sound supplementary programme for all cases where automation will not be possible. The work will also include a literature review from the perspective of size and quality, a comparing look at bibliographic resources and take into account current initiatives from research data management. One can understand the explorative procedure of this thesis as an approach to continuously question emerging concepts and thus further approach the phenomenon of data.

2. Literature review

2.1. Research Data Repositories

A repository may be defined as a set of systems and services that facilitates the ingest, storage, management, retrieval, display, and reuse of digital objects. Repositories may be set up by institutions, subject communities, research funders, or other groups. They may provide access to a variety of digital objects, including peer-reviewed journal articles, book chapters, theses, datasets, learning objects, or rich media files. (Pinfield, 2009, p. 165)

This 14-year-old definition is, besides technological advancements, still broadly valid today and will be used for the work, with a focus on research data. The inclusion criteria of re3data (registration policy) can be used supplementary as a living definition to approach repositories from a more practical perspective:

A repository must

- have a focus on research data;
- be operated by a legal entity with an organisational framework that provides sustainability (e.g., library, university);
- clarify access conditions to the repository and research data;
- and provide terms of use.

Whereby research data is understood as “[...] information objects generated in scholarly contexts, for example through experiments, measurements, surveys or interviews” (Strecker et al., 2021, pp. 5–6).

With these assumptions, we can approach some of the many works that have dealt with the repository landscape using re3data. The first larger analysis, which investigates collected attributes, used data from 2015. It reveals a heterogeneous landscape, especially in the areas of range of services and adoption of community standards (Kindling et al., 2017). Depending on the perspective, it can make sense to relate evaluations only to specific countries. With regard to India, for example, it was noted that many data repositories follow an open access data policy. However, the majority do not offer a metadata standard, and 90% do not offer persistent identifiers (Mondal, 2018, p. 50). Based on other sources besides re3data, there are surveys that deal with aspects of repositories and reveal the following with regard to their scale and in concordance to the so called long tail of science. Most repositories are limited in size (less than 1TB), more than one-third of the respondents manage repositories of between 1TB and 100TB and 8% of the repositories host data with volumes measured in petabytes. About one-fifth of the questioned repositories have grown by at least double in size over the past three years, with around half of the respondents reporting growth rates of up to 50% over the same time period (European Commission, 2022a, p. 37). In 2014 an evaluation of the repository

landscape focusing on Open Access concluded that there are a small number of large repositories (i.e. with more than one million entries) and a large number of small repositories (with 100 to 100,000 entries) (Pinfield et al., 2014, p. 2413).

2.2. Registries for Repositories

2.2.1. re3data

Several registries for repositories with different focuses have been built over time. The registry of research data repositories (re3data) is a global service that aims to index repositories from all academic disciplines. It promotes a culture of sharing and increases the visibility of repositories among its various stakeholders in the range of researchers and scholarly institutions. Ten years ago, the DFG-funded registry went live and is operated by KIT Library at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) and the Libraries of the Purdue University together with its project associates, the Berlin School of Library and Information Science at the Humboldt University of Berlin, the Helmholtz Open Science Office at the GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences and DataCite as a partner service. Re3data is a well-established service recommended by libraries, funding agencies (e.g. European Commission, National Science Foundation) as well as by publishers and journals (re3data, 2022a).

Figure 1: re3data registration workflow

(re3data, 2022b)

The workflow of re3data illustrated in figure 1 is as follows. Repositories are suggested or updated by the community and then undergo a reviewed curation workflow by re3data's International Editorial Board, which consists of researchers, research data specialists and librarians from various countries. The repository is examined automatically and with the help of an indexing handbook (Vierkant et al., 2021, pp. 3; 5). During the COREF project (Community Driven Open Reference for Research Data Repositories), the scope notes on individual fields contained there were expanded with general indexing rules and metadata quality measures maintained as a living document. The project will also produce a mapping to schema.org (see Wu et al., 2023), which also includes a discussion of the size.

Figure 2: Aspects of a Research Data Repository with the corresponding icons used in re3data.org

(Pampel et al., 2013, p. 2)

Re3data has an extensive schema to describe repositories, and these properties come together in an icon system that shows the main characteristics of the repository and helps to identify suitable repositories (Pampel et al., 2013, p. 8), which is shown in figure 2. Starting in 2020, the mentioned DFG-funded project re3data COREF (Community Driven Open Reference for Research Data Repositories) aims to improve the whole service. A focus lies on connection to other infrastructures (e.g. ROR, ORCID) to extend the technical capabilities and to increase the community experience. Concrete deliverables include, for example, updating the aforementioned metadata schema, developing a model of trust for editing and expanding and strengthening collaboration and communication with stakeholders (re3data COREF, 2021). The reuse of re3data repository descriptions in a technical way (API) for the infrastructure community is as important as the Web Interface (Weisweiler et al., 2021, p. 8) for researcher's needs and is simplified through the CC0-license for re3data database entries. Looking through different user scenarios of re3data, it seems reasonable to assume that some kind of capacity of the repository reveals important information about the underlying infrastructure. Furthermore, re3data is integrated in DataCite Commons (DataCite, 2022) and contributes to the concept of an Open Science or Persistent Identifiers Graph (Aryani et al., 2020, p. 196). Nevertheless, it must be noted that re3data, with its approximately 3000 repositories, is not a big data application, especially compared to large catalogues, article or search engine indexes.

Since schema version 1.0 (Vierkant et al., 2012) the occurrence (0-1) and definition of the size property has not changed: "The number of items contained in the research data repository". Only the range of

values evolved from “Number” to “The format is open. Example: 5.000 datasets; 30 studies” in 3.1. (Strecker et al., 2021, p. 10). The internal re3data indexing handbook assigns the optional property the priority 3 out of 3, 1 being the highest. With regard to data acquisition, the following guidance is provided:

If this information exists you can find it on the homepage or the description of the RDR (about or FAQ page). For numbers with more than four digits use the thousands separator “.” If multiple values occur (e.g. 5.000 datasets; 30 studies) use a semicolon as a delimiter and English descriptors. You can get this information also by starting an “empty search” where all datasets are displayed. If you use information about the size of a RDR please refer to it by inserting a link into the *remarksIntern* property.

These indications are to be used for both new entries (suggests) and for corrections of existing entries (change requests).

2.2.2. FAIRsharing

FAIRsharing has a similar orientation but does not only list repositories. It is “an informative and educational resource that describes and interlinks community-driven standards, databases, repositories and data policies” (Sansone et al., 2019, p. 359). At the end of 2022, the service lists 1939 databases but also 1616 standards and 156 policies, totalling 3794 records (FAIRsharing, 2022e). In their definition, databases can be knowledgebases, repositories or a mix of both. Coming from the life sciences and formerly called Biosharing (McQuilton et al., 2016), FAIRsharing has widened its scope to natural sciences, engineering, humanities and social sciences (Sansone et al., 2019, p. 359). The core FAIRsharing team consists of an operational section based at the University of Oxford and an advisory board representing different stakeholders from the publishing sector, government, academia and industry (FAIRsharing, 2022b). As a curated community service, they also strive to include external maintainers of the records and give them credit and visibility, e.g. by linking their ORCID profile to the FAIRsharing DOI of the respective record (Sansone et al., 2019, p. 359). The service lays a particularly strong focus on standards in the lifecycle of research data and, e.g. their adoption in the case of repositories. Records are also interlinked with other registries, such as re3data (Sansone et al., 2019, p. 360). Additionally, the mentioned stakeholder group of publishers finds reflection in several data policies and their recommendations (e.g. repositories) that are curated in FAIRsharing (Sansone et al., 2019, p. 362). The data is offered via an API under a Creative Commons by Share Alike 4.0 International license (FAIRsharing, 2022a).

The schema of FAIRsharing lists common attributes of a repository, such as name, homepage and data access, but does not entail information on the size of a resource or related attributes like type of

content (FAIRsharing, 2022d, 2022c). However, *publication* includes articles that can be used for citing the record. These could offer more information on the repository and act as sources for cataloguing the repository, especially for capturing an initial size.

2.2.3. OpenDOAR

If one leaves the focus of research data, other relevant directories are worth a look.

OpenDOAR is the quality-assured, global Directory of Open Access Repositories. We host repositories that provide free, open access to academic outputs and resources. Each repository record within OpenDOAR has been carefully reviewed and processed by a member of our editorial team which enables us to offer a trusted service for the community (Jisc, 2022a).

It is one of the established players in the field of repository indexation dating back to 2005 as a joint effort between the University of Nottingham and Lund University, funded by OSI, Jisc, SPARC Europe and CURL (Jisc, 2022a). A comparable service is ROAR (Registry of Open Access Repositories). Instead of manually creating records, ROAR relies on automatic harvesting, including records derived from OpenDOAR itself. These measures have advantages and disadvantages in terms of quality and quantity or immediacy of entries (Pinfield et al., 2014, p. 2408). Since OpenDOAR is most similar to re3data through its curation process, this service has been chosen here as a representative. The records are regularly monitored, and updates for records or complete new submits can be sent. In order to fulfil their mission, the repository sites need to align with their inclusion criteria but have fewer limits on the format of the repository or its content in comparison to re3data's research data focus. Only these cases are excluded:

- Site must not be an electronic journal, nor a portal for an entity's portfolio of journals
- Site must not be an aggregator which solely contains links to open access content on external sites
- Site must not be a library catalogue or collection of locally accessible e-books (i.e. no open access content is available) (Jisc, 2022a)

Going back eight years (Pinfield et al., 2014, p. 2407 f.) there was a property called size, defined as the number of records in the repository and updated every 2 to 4 weeks. It was created by a combination of elaborate automated approaches and intellectual oversight, whereby it was heavily dependent on the distinction between metadata and full-text records in the repositories.

As of 2022, their lightweight metadata schema still includes some information and a definition of the size of a repository.

- `metadata_record_count`
integer: the number of records in the repository (with or without a document attached)
- `full_text_record_count`
integer: the number of records in the repository with a document attached (Jisc, 2022b)

This information is only visible in the API, not in the GUI. Possible problems with the size field will be discussed in chapter 2.3.

2.2.4. Other Initiatives

Other initiatives deal with describing a repository but not being registries in a stricter sense. CoreTrustSeal (CTS) sees itself as “an international, community based, non-governmental, and non-profit organization promoting sustainable and trustworthy data infrastructures” (CoreTrustSeal, 2017a). Currently, 135 certified repositories are listed in the CTS portal (CoreTrustSeal, 2017b), which are also harmonised with corresponding re3data records. After a self-assessment, the repositories undergo a peer review process by CTS members to receive final certification, whereby offering a long-term preservation service is mandatory (CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board, 2022, p. 3). The CoreTrustSeal requirements 2023-2025 include various descriptions, including organisational infrastructure, digital object management and information technology & security. Where possible, indicating publicly available evidence links is considered very important to ensure transparency (CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board, 2022, p. 4 f.). Although there is no dedicated requirement for size, corresponding information can be taken from description texts such as background information & context (R0): “This should include information about the scope and size of data collections, data types and formats.” Also, discovery and identification (R12), storage & integrity (R14) can include hints in that direction (CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board, 2022). Thus, the certification document itself can be used as a cataloguing source for the repository or can contain references to other documents.

Starting January 1, 2022, there is an RDA working group trying to improve the comparison of research infrastructures and enable interoperability called the Data Repository Attributes WG (RDA Data Repository Attributes Working Group, 2021). Although the group has not yet produced any output due to its recent formation, it does represent key stakeholders (e.g. from mentioned registries) and preliminary works, thus fuelling discussions around critical issues of repository description. The concept of size was discussed initially in a property labelled content/format and addressed problems in the process but was omitted in one of the next versions. Besides working groups, there are also higher principles worth mentioning. The TRUST principles, for example, are abstract, non-technical guidelines for repositories to incorporate the FAIR principles and provide trustworthy infrastructures. TRUST stands for Transparency, Responsibility, User Focus, Sustainability and Technology (Lin et al.,

2020). The size property of a repository can be loosely mapped to the transparency principle giving users a closer view of what is inside the box in terms of volume and count. Furthermore, the user focus principle states the usage of community-accepted file formats, metrics and other standards. This can also be applied to units and granularity. The COAR Community Framework for Good Practices in Repositories offers several essential and desired characteristics in the sense of good practice for repositories. Granularity is addressed in as discoverability as follows: “In the case of research data, the repository supports identifiers for data at multiple levels of granularity, where appropriate (for example, if there is research using a subset of the full dataset and a citation of the data subset is needed)” (Shearer, 2022). Like in many other guidelines, the use of PIDs is recommended. There are also initiatives coming from a certain scientific domain, such as ELIXIR (European life-sciences Infrastructure for biological Information) for the life sciences, that have developed indicators for identifying core data resources. In the indicator “scientific focus and quality”, the “comprehensiveness of the resource” is mentioned. Furthermore, the “quality of service” touches the content of the repository through “data availability - access services and formats” (Durinx et al., 2017). Thereby, a link to size and granularity is evident. The actual profiles list heterogeneous size information under key facts (Drysdale & Martin, 2019). When we shed our view on the many curated lists of repositories that are out there, e.g. by funders such as NIH (National Institutes of Health, National Library of Medicine, 2022), size does not play a crucial role due to the scarceness of description. Alternatively, in the case of consortia tools like the NFDI4Ing Data Collections Explorer (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), 2022), size is defined as “dataset size limit (GB)”.

2.3. Data Size/Repository Size

Defining precisely what size means in the context of data or even information is a challenging task. A widely approved approach is to materialise size in the measurement of bits (Calude, 2009, p. 79) and to build up units of information like byte in a standard range of SI prefixes for the power of 10, such as kilo or peta for volume or storage. One could also proceed from an angle where data is explicitly labelled for its size: big data “[...] largely had been interpreted initially according to the ‘3 Vs’: volume, variety, and velocity. Volume refers to the increasing amount of data; variety refers to the complexity and range of data types and sources; and velocity refers to the speed of data, particularly the rate of data creation and availability” (Schintler & McNeely, 2022, p. 80). Unfortunately, neither approach sheds much light when it comes to counting or comparing digital objects in a structural way. Here the concept of granularity can help, which is closely linked to size information. To begin with, a broad definition states: “granularity concerns the ability to represent and operate on different levels of detail in data, information, and knowledge that are located at their appropriate level. The entities are described relative to that level, which may be more coarse-grained or concern fine-grained details” (Keet, 2013). This characterisation can be complemented by a more application-oriented view in data

science which illustrates the scalability in the form that “granular data can be aggregated and disaggregated to meet the needs of different situations” (Dhamdhere, 2020, p. 151).

In an ongoing RDA working group, the effort is made to provide guidance for data professionals using granularity as a lens for looking at other RDA outputs and taking into account all phases of the data life cycle: discovery, access, interoperability and citability. “Data infrastructure is generally built around predefined levels of aggregation for datasets and collections, for which conventions vary from one repository to the next” (RDA Data Granularity Working Group, 2021, p. 2). The group has not produced a dedicated output yet, but ongoing concepts include these levels of granularity:

- Measurement: One single measurement or result, e.g. a data point or single number. Alternative term--datum.
- Variable: A series of single values measured in the same way across all entities measured in the dataset, e.g. a column in a spreadsheet, a survey question and its possible response choice
- File: One file with multiple measurements or results, e.g. a spreadsheet
- Instrument (of data collection: E.g., a particular sensor)
- Custom subset: A user-created selection of a part/parts of a dataset for a purpose
- Dataset: A package of data deliberately published, typically comprised of multiple files, which would be represented by a record in a data catalogue
- Custom combination: A user-created grouping of datasets or subset thereof (e.g., results from a search (w/its own resolvable URL), combined locally by the end user, etc.)
- Collection (of datasets): A repository-created grouping of datasets (e.g., fixed in some way, collected for a thematic or administrative reason) (RDA Data Granularity Working Group, 2023)

For the purpose of this thesis, the collection could be interpreted on the highest level as a repository. Also, many metadata standards have implemented a property that deals with size on a data level. The DataCite Schema is a domain agnostic standard and defines it as “size (e.g., bytes, pages, inches, etc.) or duration (extent), e.g., hours, minutes, days, etc., of a resource “. The field is optional, repeatable and containing free text along with these examples: “15 pages”, “6 MB”, “45 minutes” (DataCite Metadata Working Group, 2021, p. 26). That covers duration and extent and contains highly varying information through its open format like re3data. ISO 19115-1 is an example of a disciplinary metadata standard dealing with geospatial information. In its package distribution information (MD_Distribution), which provides metadata for obtaining a resource, the optional field *transferSize* uses this definition: “estimated size of a unit in the specified transfer format, expressed in megabytes NOTE The transfer size is > 0,0” with the data type real (DIN Deutsches Institut für Normung e. V, 2014, p. 70). This more practical approach focuses on the volume aspect of size. Reference should also be made here to the excursus in chapter 2.5. on bibliographic resources as it covers a related standard.

When counting digital objects, it is also difficult to determine whether the “real” digital objects (full text) or only their references are counted. In the case of OpenDOAR, the harvester could not distinguish between full text and metadata-only records, thus driving the numbers up by factor 10 (Pinfield et al., 2014, p. 2413 f.). Furthermore, it is not clear how exactly to deal with copies, e.g. if a research file has been published in two repositories.

How does this all come together in a repository, and what is the size of a repository? Let us have a look at size information and how it was presented by a repository itself:

First, some high level statistics (as at March 2014):

- Number of items: 125
- Total number of files: 1946
- Mean number of files per item: 16
- Total disk space used by files: 76GB (0.074TB) (Lewis, 2014)

Size fields promise reliable and transparent information, but the property is rather controversial and often contains unclear or unstructured information that can rapidly change. As we have seen, size can be interpreted in many ways, such as capacity, volume, extent, scale or quantity. Besides the actual property, other attributes can be related to the concept, especially when it comes to granularity issues: type of resource, relationship between resources or format information.

2.4. Metadata Quality

Size in the context of repositories and especially as a descriptive property of re3data is considered a form of metadata. Metadata can be defined as “structured information associated with an object for purposes of discovery, description, use, management, and preservation” (NISO Framework Working Group, 2007, p. 58). As already mentioned in the previous chapters, the issue of quality touches all areas of research infrastructure and is also crucial for both the creation and curation of metadata. The literature often argues that quality should be somehow in line with “fitness for purpose”, i.e., the degree to which an object supports a certain function (Király, 2019, p. 1). In the case of metadata of repositories, this purpose includes diverse and also changing needs of stakeholders like researchers, funders, repository operators, policymakers, data stewards and other research data infrastructure representatives. Therefore, this expression of metadata quality should be divided into its individual functions and evaluated regularly. On a more abstract level, different metadata quality indicators have been developed catering to the needs of their specific community. In addition, the concept of curation, which can be seen as the basis of the dimensions, should be explicitly mentioned here (Kaiser et al., 2020, p. 5). It anchors the quality aspirations in the real world and creates the link to the research infrastructure facilities. When it comes to the quality of indexing, institutes can first rely on basic

dimensions of quality assurance, such as trustworthiness and transparency regarding data and indexing rules. Topics of higher quality dimensions include contextualisation of rules and standards for data description as well as evaluation for classical and non-classical retrieval and display (Expertenteams RDA-Anwendungsprofil für die verbale Inhaltserschließung (ET RAVI), 2021, p. 115 ff.). Based on the data quality metrics of (Bruce & Hillmann, 2004), which represents a generic but established concept, the author will summarise and adapt these according to the scope of the work as follows:

Completeness:

The element set used should describe the resource as completely as economically feasible. As many metadata elements of the element set should be used to describe a repository as extensively as possible.

Accuracy¹:

The metadata values need to be correct and factual in comparison to what is described. Furthermore, the values should be free of typographical errors, express names conformingly and use standard abbreviations. In large or heterogeneous collections, accuracy may be verified indirectly via sampling techniques or automated alternatives.

Provenance:

Information on how and when the metadata was created or transformed, that is, persons, methodologies etc., can improve transparency and trustworthiness.

Conformance to Expectations:

Element sets should contain those elements that the community would reasonably expect to find and use suitable controlled vocabularies. They should not contain elements that are not likely to be used because they are superfluous or irrelevant. Regarding implementation, practical compromises should lead the decisions.

Logical Consistency and Coherence:

Metadata should comply with standard definitions and should be coherent across and within registries.

Timeliness:

Metadata should describe the resource in its current form and should be kept in sync with updates of the resource.

¹ Not to be confused with *size_non_unit_type* mentioned in chapter 4.1.1.

Accessibility:

Metadata should be readable and understandable by the users minimising intellectual or physical barriers.

As mentioned, there are more and also other compilations of dimensions (Palavitsinis, 2013, p. 62 ff.). Objectiveness in the sense of an unbiased description, for example, seems difficult to measure and can also be subsumed roughly under “conformance to expectations”. The question of the (multi-)linguality of metadata is also not easy to measure and will only be considered in terms of coherence for the purpose of this thesis. The last quality indicator, “accessibility”, leads to a concept that deals especially with the publication of research data and culminates in the FAIR principles. Since re3data repository descriptions serve research purposes, keeping these criteria in mind makes sense. However, this does not address whether repositories themselves are considered FAIR-enabling or if re3data is a FAIR-enabling service/repository (see e.g. d’Aquin et al., 2022).

With regard to the re3data service, the following points can be noted concerning concrete metadata quality. There is a divergence between the published schema version in re3data and the adopted one in the running service. For example, in the case of *policyType*, where the running service does not apply all existing values from the schema (Kim & Choi, 2017, p. 44). Furthermore, some fields suggest standardisation but standardisation is not directly present in the background. Institutions are not merged in re3data at the current time due to historical technical reasons, i.e. one or more institutions are attached to each repository but not vice versa (n-m relation). Thus, there are different recordings of the same institution, which may differ marginally, but can lead to less usable data (quality) (Kim, 2018, p. 81). Problems can exist with the occurrence of a field, which also raises the question of importance. For example, the *subject* field is obligatory according to the scheme but not in the current service. There were cases of repositories not using that field; the same applies to *dataUpload*. Especially if an optional field is almost always used, suspicion should be raised, and considerations of making it mandatory or a check for new controlled vocabulary should be applied. In the case of *institutionType* (commercial, non-profit) covering a broad semantic scope, just a small amount of institutions did not use this field, pointing more to the conclusion of human error in indexing than to a missing controlled term. The same applies to keywords (*keyword*) that have been assigned consistently but are optional (Kim & Choi, 2017, pp. 45–46) And finally, there is the problem of missing values when metadata is applied in research, which brings its own difficulties and cannot be remedied across the board but only hinted at here (Harrell, 2015).

2.5. The Bibliographic World: Resource Description and Access (RDA)

The description of resources has a long tradition in the cataloguing of bibliographic material. Therefore, it makes sense to look at the situation there to find corresponding similarities and differences to the

world of research data. The current predominant framework for cataloguing is called Resource Description and Access (RDA). RDA is based on IFLA LRM (International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions Library Reference Model) as a conceptual data model and, therefore, consistent with other descriptive standards that rely on IFLA LRM (Oliver, 2021, p. 207).

RDA pays particular attention to the quality of data. The standard is used to declare, accurately:

- type of content (for example, text, annotated music, performed music, cartographic image, computer program, sounds, the spoken word);
- type of media (a higher level - the means by which the content is communicated, for example, microform, audio, projection, video);
- type of format (a lower level or a specific level, since it refers to the kind of format for a type of media - how the content is packaged; for example, for videos, the format can be: video cartridges, video cassettes, tape reel, video disc);
- modes of issuance (how the resource is issued, for example, as a single unit, a monograph in multiple parts, a serial, or an integrating resource). (Guerrini, 2016, p. 93 f.)

Here the dependence on a carrier medium becomes visible, which does not play a substantial role in the case of data or repositories. Nevertheless, the concept of an integrating resource (e.g., an updating website) in its current iteration can be adopted, and the attribute *extent* can be compared to size.

ID	Entity	Attribute	Definition
LRM-E4-A2	MANIFESTATION	Extent	A quantification of the extent observed on a physical carrier of the <i>manifestation</i> and assumed to be observable on all other physical carriers of the <i>manifestation</i> as well
	Scope notes	<p>The value of the <i>extent</i> attribute consists of three elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - a type of extent (e.g., numbering of physical units, height, width, diameter, etc.), - a number, - and a measurement unit (e.g., volumes, pages, sheets, discs, reels, etc.; cm, inches, etc.; Mb/Megabytes; etc.). <p>The type of extent and the measurement unit may be given implicitly. The level of precision used in recording the quantification of the extent may vary.</p>	
	Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 300 ## \$a 301 p., [8] p. of plates [number of pages, recorded according to AACR2 and expressed in a MARC 21 subfield] • 215 ## \$a 1 score (vi, 63 p.) \$d 20 cm \$a 16 parts \$d 32 cm \$e 1 booklet [number of pages, and their height; number of parts, and their height; and number of accompanying material elements, expressed in various subfields of a UNIMARC field] • 4 3/4 in. [diameter, expressed in natural language, in English] 	

Figure 3: IFLA LRM-E4-A2 Extent

(IFLA Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR) Review Group et al., 2018, p. 48)

In figure 3 the definition of the attribute extent in the IFLA-LRM is shown. The mix of numbers and strings as values comes naturally, and no fixed types of units are predefined. The RDA Toolkit (American Library Association, 2017, p. 3.4) provides additional information. The extent is mandatory for complete manifestations or if the total extent is known. As the source of information, the so-called manifestation itself (or on any accompanying material or container) is recommended, and the possibility to take additional evidence from any source is given. In addition, a list of carrier types is provided (e.g. online resource) that can be extended with subunits and new terms in their common usage.

Interestingly, if the exact number of units is not readily ascertainable, it can also be estimated (“approximately 600 slides”). If the units cannot be named concisely, they should be recorded as “various pieces”. Subunits can also be counted individually, e.g. “1 computer tape (3 data files: 100, 460, 550 records)” or “1 online resource (1 program file: 96 statements)” if they are easily detectable and important. When describing collections as a whole, the mentioned options can also be extended by the method of storage space as a concept, e.g. “1 m³, 40 linear ft., 4.5 m (12 boxes, approximately 1000 items)”. It must be noted that in many places, the creation of attribute values comes with a rather optional character or the responsibility is passed to the cataloguer (Wiesenmüller & Horny, 2017, pp. 28–29). In actual implementation, e.g. in library catalogues, at least in the German-speaking community, the author has noticed less detailed information on size for similar entities such as databases. If present at all, the information was scarce: “1 Online-Ressource”. As when describing repositories, there can also be a relation between the size and type of content in RDA. Aggregate and component entities that are related to granularity, are topics that have been discussed since the beginning of RDA’s establishment (Taniguchi, 2013) but are not presented here due to their inherent difference that lies in the concept of work, expression, manifestation and item.

3. Methodology

To converge the research question around the size property of repositories, a combined approach looked most promising. In chapter 3.1. a more quantitative method is applied to the indexed metadata in a registry of repositories (re3data). Then the data basis will be extended with a qualitative case study to draw a comparison between already indexed metadata in a registry and actual repositories. From a theoretical point of view, this covers data and methodological triangulation to test for consistency between different data sources producing the same results. Possible inconsistencies are seen as enriching the research design rather than weakening it (Patton, 2002, p. 247 f.).

3.1. Data Analysis of re3data

3.1.1. Property Selection

Regarding property selection, a comprehensive approach was taken regarding re3data's metadata schema currently used by the API (Vierkant et al., 2014). That includes basic repository information, size information or fields that are combinable or affiliated with size. All properties are documented in the documentation, which is linked in Appendix C. Besides the analysis of re3data's data, an expansive dataset enables a proper selection of repositories for the case study (see chapter 3.2). Therefore, the remaining properties would not have benefitted the analysis directly and were left out. Country and language would have been possible to widen the scope with a regional dimension, but these are only reflected indirectly in the case study.

3.1.2. Data Extraction

The data was extracted from the re3data API on 26.11.2022 using an adaption (see Appendix C) of the re3data API Jupyter Notebooks (re3data, 2022c). The script was run in R 4.0.2 in JupyterLab Version 3.2.1 via the Jülich Supercomputing Centre (JSC) in two instances (production, backup) for reasons of easy accessibility and stability. The results are version 1 (v1) of the dataset. Alternatively, it would have been possible to use an offline SQL dump of the re3data database. Since this would have included additional IT effort and less reproducibility, the idea was discarded. The advantages of a dump would have been that internal re3data fields and not indexed repositories would have also been available. These restrictions are pointed out in the relevant passages.

3.1.3. Data Processing

Data processing included two main automated actions that are also performed in R. First, the size property, which includes unstructured content, was split up by numbers resulting in two new columns *size_number* (numeric content) and *size_unit* (alphabetic content). Then outside of size, foreseeable normalisations were performed. The values *unknown* and *none* were deleted in the properties *softwareName*, *pidSystem* and *enhancedPublication*. The values mentioned do not offer any additional semantic value, are assigned inconsistently and generally correspond to an unassigned (empty) value

for an attribute. For the attributes *startDate* and *endDate*, the date format was simplified to year numbers due to different granularity (e.g. 2002-12-31. vs 2002-12 vs 2002). The *updated* attribute, which also contains date information, remained untouched at that point since it is important for the research question. The remained dataset is named v2.

It should be noted that residual values such as “other” were not taken into account (*softwareName*, *apiType*, *certificate*, *metadataStandardName*). As mentioned earlier, these are free-text values that are collected internally by re3data for emerging values but cannot be retrieved via the API. In future schema versions, these will be converted piece by piece into controlled vocabulary and then be publicly available.

3.1.4. Data Typing

The third version of the dataset (v3) contains manual actions on the data. Beforehand a regular expression splitting up units and number of size was created extra narrowly to explore irregularities on sight. Then manual corrections were applied in these two fields for all generated exceptions and errors. For *size_unit* these included mostly: complex or phrase-like units, composites and units with commas, units with numbers or special characters in them. For *size_number*, remaining separators were deleted, numbers as words transformed using the short scale and percentages converted except fixed units like TB. All remaining non-unit, non-number content was typed in *size_non_unit_type*. Since all of this is directly related to quality issues, the *size_quality* field was created and filled along the way, according to observations. Whitespaces and additional punctuation marks were only considered when they were syntax relevant, e.g. for separation. In order not to inflate the values for syntax error, the part-of relation (see following paragraph) between units was not consistently counted as such. Nevertheless, it can also be evaluated as a syntax error.

The guideline for detailed unit separation that emerged was that the unit is able to stand on its own, that omissible content was separated and that the unit is comprehensible in relation to other mentioned units (e.g. “public” vs “private” data). In case of doubt, all columns dealing with size information were used for typing the following columns, and in general, a certain overlap and vagueness between the fields remains. The new columns dealing with different dimensions of the size unit are *size_unit_type* (quantity vs volume), *size_unit_discipline* (generic vs disciplinary), *size_unit_content* (neutral vs other).

All typed fields (*size_unit_type*, *size_unit_discipline*, *size_unit_content*, *size_non_unit_type*, *size_quality*) refer to whole repository records, not to the value of *size_number* and *size_unit*. This is due to the fact that units make sense in context of the whole repository but not on its own e.g. ambiguous units such as “token”. Along the way, internal quality checks (e.g. for empty values) were

performed, whereby a certain error rate could probably not be avoided without the principle of multiple eyes. Finally, the *updated* property was classified in terms of quality in the field *updated_quality* (e.g. no corresponding size), and the errors were eliminated in *updated_corrected*.

Exploding the categories for content (*size_unit_content*), the planned complete typing of the data was not possible. Therefore, a two-step approach was chosen. First, the mentioned subdivision into neutral and other units, i.e. whether initial indications of the content were recognisable or not. In the second step, the dataset was uncollapsed and columns besides *re3data.orgIdentifier*, *size_number*, *size_unit*, *size_unit_content* and were dropped (v4). This enabled the author to come to the individual unit level, and examples of the other values worth showing were identified. Since a clear separation between typing and analysis is difficult here, it was integrated into the Jupyter Notebook of the analysis (see also the following section 3.1.5). As mentioned, an areal-depth typing was not possible, as this would have required a deeper knowledge of disciplinary units and or natural language processing for the 4293 units. The recalcitrance of a categorisation of *size_content* is precisely a realisation that will be illuminated in the analysis. Therefore, only some peculiar and model units were highlighted in the dataset as *size_unit_content_other* with three examples per categorisation to illustrate the typing problems. To get a practical application of the concept of granularity, the most common unit, “dataset”, was also counted. Here, only units were deliberately adopted in which the original notation occurs, and no influencing decisions had to be made.

3.1.5. Data Analysis

The quantitative analysis includes univariate and multivariate analysis for chosen subsets of attributes included. Rather basic properties (e.g. *repositoryURL*) were skipped, and also, *subject* and *keyword* were left out because they were too far away from the research questions, but can be considered a desiderate. For more minor calculations, on-the-fly data modifications were applied that appeared necessary, but no fully normalized variables, such as in chapter 3.1.3. were created. These are all documented in the Jupyter Notebook (see Appendix C). The selection of univariate properties is based on the possibility of shedding light on the size of a repository and included:

- *repositoryIdentifier*

The OpenDOAR identifier was chosen to show possible automation possibilities. According to research, the other identifiers/services do not offer direct size information. In addition, NA and the remaining residual values were presented as frequencies to provide an overview.

- *description*

Possible size information was detected by simple number matching and shown for repositories that already have size information and repositories that have not. In addition, NA values were presented as frequencies to provide an overview.

- *size*

Full values and NA values were presented as frequencies. Detailed observations will follow in the next fields.

- *size_number, size_unit*

The sample was expanded to get to the individual unit level (not repository level) and all other columns besides *re3data.orgIdentifier*, *size_number*, *size_unit* except *size_unit_content* were dropped. NA values were mutually represented for *size_number* and *size_unit*. Furthermore, the frequencies of several units per repository were listed. In order to create theoretical comparability, the relation between *size_number* and *size_unit* was only created for the “datasets” unit as an example; other granularity units like “variables” were not that common. Only minimum and maximum were calculated since no real comparability was given.

- *size_unit_type*

The sample was shortened to the ones that have a size value (size full), and controlled values are presented as frequencies.

- *size_unit_discipline*

The sample was shortened to the ones that have a size value (size full), and controlled values are presented as frequencies.

- *size_unit_content*

The sample was shortened to the ones that have a size value (size full), and controlled values are presented as frequencies.

- *size_unit_content_other*

This is an intellectual completion of the typification of *size_content* with three examples each for the discovered content levels.

- *size_non_unit_type*

The sample was shortened to the ones that have a size value (size full), and controlled values are presented as frequencies. Multiple values per repository can occur, and combinations were not considered relevant.

- *size_quality*

The sample was shortened to the ones that have a size value (size full), and controlled values are presented as frequencies. Multiple values per repository can occur, and combinations were considered relevant, but not visualized.

- *updated_quality*

The sample was shortened to the ones that have a size value (size full), and controlled values are presented as frequencies. Values outside the sample (*updated_quality* issues but size field not occupied) are listed separately.

- *providerType*

Controlled values are presented as frequencies.

- *databaseAccessType*

Controlled values are presented as frequencies.

- *dataUploadType*

Controlled values for “closed” and coarsened values for the rest are presented as frequencies. Multiple values per repository can occur, and combinations were not considered relevant.

- *softwareName*

Controlled values are presented as frequencies. Multiple values per repository can occur, and combinations were not considered relevant.

- *apiType*

Controlled values are presented as frequencies. Multiple values per repository can occur, and combinations were not considered relevant.

- *pidSystem*

Controlled values are presented as frequencies. Multiple values per repository can occur, and combinations were not considered relevant.

- *enhancedPublication*

Controlled values together with NA are presented as frequencies.

- *certificate*

NA values and coarsened values for all remaining certificates are presented as frequencies. Multiple values per repository can occur, and combinations were not considered relevant.

- *metadataStandardName*

Although DublinCore is one of the most widely used metadata standards, the DataCite metadata standard was chosen for the analysis because it focuses more on research data. In addition to this generic standard, ISO 19115 was selected as an example of a disciplinary standard. The remaining standards were grouped together as a remainder and listed alongside NA values. Multiple values per repository can occur, and combinations were not considered relevant.

- *remarks*

Possible size information was detected by simple number matching and shown for repositories that already have size information and repositories that have not. In addition, NA values were presented as frequencies to provide an overview.

Since the thesis focuses on the size property itself extensive multivariate analyses with all properties were not purposeful. However, it seemed promising to have a closer look at some of the newly typed *size_unit* properties among each other:

- *size_unit_discipline*, *size_unit_content* in view of Pearson's product-moment correlation. As a first approximation to the data, and because this variable has been treated at the repository level rather than the unit level, only very strong correlations have been considered.

Another focus is combinations of size properties in relation to time:

- *updated_corrected*, *entryDate*, *lastUpdate* are closely linked to quality assurance. Comparing *updated_corrected* and *lastUpdate* produces implausibilities that were corrected (set to *lastUpdate*) afterwards. Comparing *entryDate* and *lastUpdate* gives insight in debatable temporal size information. Measure of location (mean) and statistical dispersion (interquartile

range) were chosen for *updated_corrected* and the difference between *lastUpdate* and *updated_corrected* (*dif_update_last*) due to robustness against outliers. Time information outside of this (*startDate* of the repository or current date) was not taken into account.

3.2. Case Study of Sample Repositories

In an exploratory case study, individual repositories were investigated on an autoptic level. Since there are many definitions of a case study, this research design uses its basic definition as “an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context; when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident; and in which multiple sources of evidence are used” (Yin & Yin, 2008, p. 23). One reason for this was to supplement the data analysis of re3data with additional source data from websites, documents, APIs or internal files. Another reason was to compare the size-relevant values in re3data to the sources and take a closer look at them in the context of the original repository to detect possible quality issues.

In order to achieve this, four repositories were chosen by purposive sampling, in a mixture of a priori sampling and snowball sampling (Pickard, 2013, p. 64). The next paragraph covers the first, and the following paragraph covers the last method, which is an inductive technique throughout the research benefiting from cases that appeared in chapter 3.1. The focus of this whole sampling method lies in selecting information-rich cases, where “information-rich cases are those from which one can learn a great deal about issues of central importance to the purpose of the research [...]” (Patton, 2002, p. 46).

The selection criteria include different approaches. One is the variability or existence of basic re3data properties: *repositoryIdentifier*, *type*, *startDate*, *contentType*, *databaseAccessType*, *softwareName*, *apiType*, *pidSystem* and supplementary: *subjects*, *keyword* (see Appendix C: documentation.txt). All other properties were considered less important for the selection or will be analysed as a whole, e.g. size information in other re3data fields (e.g. *description*). Offline repositories were skipped due to their limited informative value but are also considered as whole in the re3data analysis in chapter 4.1. As mentioned in chapter 3.1.1., region or language was not the focus of this research, and so language was not extracted from the API and used directly. However, the language of a repository is somewhat relevant to general indexing of repositories and can carry a burden, although almost all repositories have at least one English version. So by narrowing down case sets, language variety was considered (Bilkent University Institutional Repository - BUIR, ScienceDB), and language could have been included in the original API extract (*repositoryLanguage*). Another selection criterion was including samples with and without size values to represent both parts of the records in re3data. It should be noted that the cases without size values are very sparse and it was not the purpose of the method to make statements for all cases with empty size values or any other generalisations (see Pickard, 2013, p. 67).

Finally, the types created in chapter 3.1. were used (*size_unit_type*, *size_unit_discipline*, *size_unit_content*, *size_non_unit_type*, *size_quality*) to find common or exotic repositories cases and two evaluate empty size repositories too, if applicable. *updated_quality* was considered less important due to its tendency to be a human error. Very old cases regarding *updated* are not covered directly but the timeliness of updating a repository is considered in both examples with size values (Inorganic Crystal Structure Database - ICSD, ScienceDB). All aspects of cases that were dismissed along the selection process were considered as a whole in the quantitative analysis. The author's experience in cataloguing repositories was used in case of doubt when selecting similar repositories.

The repositories were accessed with a standard browser (Firefox 102.7.0 esr - 64-bit) under Windows 10 Enterprise in a private network and from the KIT network if necessary. Captured data (Appendix A) was structured similarly for every case where possible, including an overview, date of retrieval, GUI, API, other sources and internal. It includes textual or numeric quotes from sources and screenshots where "look and feel" were important, or text data was not easily retrievable. Older site versions were retrieved via the WaybackMachine. The colours in the screenshots of re3data are reversed due to technical modalities: green is older, and red is newer. The reference URLs are organised as simple footnotes rather than fully formatted references as a distinction between this raw data report for the case studies and intellectual resources in the thesis document. Adopted contents have been treated as quotations, and additions by the author have been marked with brackets.

4. Results

4.1. Data Analysis

4.1.1. Univariate

repositoryIdentifier

Figure 4: repositoryIdentifier

Figure 4 shows that out of 3037 repositories, 1922 (63.3%) have no value for *repositoryIdentifier*, and 1073 (35.3%) have any value except OpenDOAR, and 42 (1.4%) have OpenDOAR identifiers.

description

Figure 5: description

Figure 5 shows that out of 3037 repositories, 1956 (64.4%) do not have possible size information in the *description*. 1081 (35.6%) have possible size information in the *description*: 590 (19.4%) when the size value is empty and 491 (16.2%) when the size value is full.

size

Figure 6: size

Figure 6 shows that out of 3037 repositories, 1495 (49.2%) have a size value, and 1542 (50.8%) have no size value.

size_number and size_unit

Out of the 4293 individual size numbers and units, 1547 have no values, one has a unit value and no corresponding size number (r3d100011560: “community uploads”), and seven have a number with no corresponding size as shown in figure 7:

re3data.orgIdentifier	size_number	size_unit
r3d100010157	47995	NA
r3d100010545	0	NA
r3d100010211	289227	NA
r3d100011480	23270	NA
r3d100010132	49	NA
r3d100011503	3718390	NA
r3d100010641	401	NA

Figure 7: size_number with no size_unit

Out of the 4293 individual size units, 442 (10.3%) contain the unit “dataset” and a corresponding *size_number*. The highest value for datasets is 12.148.116 (r3d100012628) and the smallest is one dataset (r3d100011810, r3d100012488, r3d100012997, r3d100013637, r3d100011804, r3d100013932).

Figure 8: *size_unit per repository*

The frequency of multiple units per repository shown in figure 8 is as follows: 2405 times one unit, 269 times two units, 245 times three units, 66 times four units, 20 times five units, 14 times six units, three times seven units, four times nine units, one time 12 units, two times 13 units and one time 16 units.

size_unit_type

Figure 9: size_unit_type

Figure 9 shows that from 1495 repositories, 1400 (93.7%) include quantity units, 39 (2.6%) quantity and volume units (bytes), 38 (2.5%) pure volume units, and 18 (1.2%) have no *size_unit_type*.

size_unit_discipline

Figure 10: *size_unit_discipline*

Figure 10 shows that from 1495 repositories, 931 (64.9%) include generic units, 353 (23.6%) include disciplinary units, 160 (10.7%) have generic and disciplinary units, and 12 (0.8%) have no *size_unit_discipline*.

size_unit_content

Figure 11: size_unit_content

Figure 11 shows that from 1495 repositories, 884 (59.1%) have neutral size units, 473 (31.6%) have other size units, 126 (8.4%) have neutral or other size units, and 12 (0.8%) have no *size_unit_content*.

size_unit_content_other

re3data.orgIdentifier	size_number	size_unit	size_unit_content	size_unit_content_other
r3d100012239	247	pieces of information for each case	other	abstract
r3d100012727	6504	Ontology Terms	other	abstract
r3d100011950	30	models	neutral other	abstract
r3d100010363	140000	images	other	file
r3d100012058	900	publications	neutral other	file
r3d100013238	1905	software packages	other	file
r3d100011192	280606	analyses	other	method
r3d100013187	31	functional genomics experiments	other	method
r3d100013666	6	multi-centric studies	neutral other	method
r3d100010582	700	TFlops computing power	other	nodata
r3d100011697	107	contributing members	neutral other	nodata
r3d100011561	8000000	hits each month	neutral other	nodata
r3d100010766	7730	Unoriented Low Resolution Raman Spectra	other	physical
r3d100013228	900	mouse samples	other	physical
r3d100013302	37606	clinical trials	other	physical

Figure 12: size_unit_content_other

Figure 12 shows selected values from *size_unit_content* containing the value other that are subtyped more specifically in five new values (*size_unit_content_other*) with three examples for each case.

size_non_unit_type

Figure 13: *size_non_unit_type*

Figure 13 shows that from 1495 repositories, 1182 (79.1%) repositories have no *size_non_unit_type*, 197 (13%) contain accuracy² information, 83 (5.6%) contain part-of-information (partof), 80 (5.4%) contain omittable information, 19 (1.3%) contain detail information, and 10 (0.7%) contain entirety information.

² Not to be confused with the metadata quality dimension mentioned in chapter 2.4.

size_quality

Figure 14: size_quality

Figure 14 shows that out of 1495 repositories, 1118 have no indication of size quality issues (74.8%), 187 (12.5%) show syntax errors, 126 (8.4%) dot errors, 78 (5.2%) number errors, 44 (2.9%) comma errors, 24 (1.6%) semantic errors, 16 (1.1%) orthographic errors, 14 (0.9%) distribution errors, 9 (0.6%) language errors and 6 (0.4%) show issues with range.

one error	count
syntax error	105
dot error	80
number error	32
semantic error	16
comma error	15
orthographic error	10
language error	4
distribution error	3
range	2
	267

Figure 15: size_quality one error

Figure 15 shows the distribution of a single error with 267 times total. Syntax errors occur most frequently alone, and ranges occur least frequently on their own.

two errors	count
dot error syntax error	33
comma error number error	13
syntax error number error	9
syntax error distribution error	7
number error syntax error	6
semantic error syntax error	4
number error range	3
comma error dot error	2
comma error syntax error	2
distribution error syntax error	2
dot error language error	2
dot error orthographic error	2
dot error semantic error	2
syntax error language error	2
syntax error orthographic error	2
dot error number error	1
language error number error	1
orthographic error syntax error	1
	94

Figure 16: size_quality two errors

Figure 16 shows the distribution of two errors at once with 94 times total in 18 combinations. Dot errors and syntax errors occur most frequently; dot errors and number errors, language errors and number errors as well as orthographic errors and syntax errors occur just one time.

three errors	count
comma error number error syntax error	9
comma error semantic error syntax error	2
comma error dot error number error	1
distribution error dot error syntax error	1
distribution error orthographic error syntax error	1
dot error number error range	1
dot error number error syntax error	1
	16

Figure 17: size_quality three errors

Figure 17 shows the distribution of three errors simultaneously with 16 times total in seven combinations. Comma errors and number errors and syntax errors is the most frequent error combination.

updated_quality

Figure 18: updated_quality

Figure 18 shows that out of 1495 repositories, 1455 (97.3%) present no quality error for (size) *updated*. 19 (1.3%) present a format error, 12 (0.8%) are missing an *updated* value for size, five (0.3%) show granularity issues, three (0.1%) have no corresponding size value, and one (<0.1%) has an implausible size value (“2917-04-04”) that is too high.

providerType

Figure 19: providerType

Figure 19 shows that out of 3037 repositories, 1990 are dataProvider (65.5%), 789 are dataProvider and serviceProvider (26%), 253 are serviceProvider (8.3%), and 5 (0.2%) have no value for this attribute.

databaseAccessType

Figure 20: databaseAccessType

Figure 20 shows that from 3037 repositories, 2869 (94.5%) offer an open databaseAccess, 147 (4.8%) provide restricted access, and 21 offer closed access (0.7%).

dataUploadType

Figure 21: dataUploadType

Figure 21 shows that out of 3037 repositories, 916 (30.2%) provide *dataUploadType* in closed form only. The rest (2121, 69.8%) is open, restricted or a mixture of all three.

softwareName

Figure 22: softwareName

Figure 22 shows that out of 3037 repositories *softwareName* is distributed as follows: 1861 (61%) no *softwareName*, 628 (20.6%) other, 152 (5%) DataVerse, 118 (3.9%) DSpace, 91 (3%) CKAN, 88 (2.9%) MySQL, 45 (1.5%) Fedora, 34 (1.1%) EPrints, 19 (0.6%) Nesstar, five (0.2%) DigitalCommons, five (0.2%) eSciDoc, two (0.1%) Opus, two (0.1%) dlibra.

apiType

Figure 23: apiType

Figure 23 shows that out of 3037 repositories *apiType* is distributed as follows: 1648 (46.6%) no value, 611 (17.3%) REST, 335 (9.5%) FTP, 322 (9.1%) other, 276 (7.8%) OAI-PMH, 95 (2.7%) SWORD, 92 (2.6%) NetCDF, 60 (1.7%) SOAP, 52 (1.5%) OpenDAP, 46 (1.3%) SPARQL.

pidSystem

Figure 24: pidSystem

Figure 24 shows that out of 3037 repositories *pidSystem* is distributed as follows: 1789 (55.4%) no *pidSystem*, 961 (29.8%) DOI, 244 (7.6%) hdl, 120 (3.7%) other, 53 (1.6%) URN, 32 (1%) PURL, 28 (0.9%) ARK.

enhancedPublication

Figure 25: *enhancedPublication*

Figure 25 shows that out of 3037 repositories, 1814 (59.7%) have no information about *enhancedPublication*, 978 (32.2%) have *enhancedPublication* and 245 (8.1%) have no *enhancedPublication*.

certificate

Figure 26: certificate

Figure 26 shows that out of 3037 repositories, 2791 (91.9%) have no *certificate*, 246 (8.1%) have one or many certificates out of: Clarin certificate B, DIN 31664, DINI Certificate, DSA, ISO 16363, RatSWD, Trusted Digital Repository, WDS, other (contains CoreTrustSeal).

metadataStandardName

Figure 27: metadataStandardName

Figure 27 shows that out of 3037 repositories, 1822 (48%) have no metadata standard, 691 (22.8%) have one of the other metadata standards, 334 (8.8%) use DataCite Metadata Schema, 190 (5%) use ISO 19115 as a metadata standard.

remarks

Figure 28: remarks

Figure 28 shows that out of 3037 repositories, 2434 (80.1%) do not have possible size information in *remarks*. 603 (19.9%) have possible size information in *remarks*: 304 (10%) for when the size value is full and 299 (9.9%) when the size value is empty.

4.1.2. Multivariate and Time

size_unit_discipline and size_unit_content

Figure 29: size_unit_discipline and size_unit_content

The plot shows a strong correlation between generic (*size_unit_discipline*) and neutral (*size_unit_content*), with $r = 0.88$ ($t = 100.21$, $df = 3035$, $p < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$). Furthermore, a moderate to strong correlation between disciplinary (*size_unit_discipline*) and other (*size_unit_content*) can be revealed, as indicated by $r = 0.71$ ($t = 55.29$, $df = 3035$, $p < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$). All remaining values show less strong correlations ($-0.28 \leq r \leq 0.44$).

updated_corrected, entryDate, lastUpdate

re3data.orgIdentifier	entryDate	updated_corrected	lastUpdate
r3d100012570	2017-12-06	2018-10-31	2018-10-30
r3d100010966	2014-09-01	2021-11-21	2021-08-24
r3d100013470	2020-12-17	2022-02-22	2022-02-21
r3d100011942	2016-02-19	2022-06-16	2022-05-16

Figure 30: Implausibilities between *updated_corrected* and *lastUpdate*

Figure 30 shows implausibilities between *updated_corrected* and *lastUpdate* documented by four repositories where *updated_corrected* is greater than *lastUpdate*.

re3data.orgIdentifier	entryDate	updated_corrected	lastUpdate
r3d100012571	2017-12-06	2017-03-01	2017-12-23
r3d100013033	2019-04-10	2018-04-10	2020-07-08
r3d100010894	2014-08-15	2014-08-06	2021-10-06
r3d100012841	2018-08-27	2018-08-12	2021-11-16
r3d100013775	2022-03-10	2019-10-01	2022-03-12
r3d100013508	2021-02-22	2020-02-24	2022-04-25
r3d100010586	2014-01-14	2012-05-01	2019-02-21
r3d100010080	2012-11-27	2012-11-26	2021-08-24
r3d100012728	2018-07-04	2016-04-18	2021-09-03
r3d100012768	2018-07-27	2017-07-01	2018-08-01
r3d100011378	2014-12-10	2014-11-12	2021-12-22
r3d100012171	2016-09-27	2016-04-01	2017-11-21
r3d100012684	2018-05-21	2018-01-15	2018-08-14
r3d100013014	2019-03-27	2019-03-08	2019-03-30
r3d100012917	2018-12-13	2013-01-01	2021-09-02
r3d100013835	2022-05-19	2022-05-14	2022-05-22
r3d100013992	2022-10-18	2020-10-20	2022-10-22
r3d100011489	2015-04-15	2015-04-14	2018-08-15
r3d100011533	2015-03-16	2014-03-18	2019-12-17
r3d100012763	2018-07-18	2018-07-01	2021-08-25
r3d100011539	2015-02-23	2014-12-31	2022-04-12
r3d100011841	2016-04-29	2016-04-26	2022-05-06
r3d100012565	2017-11-29	2017-01-18	2017-12-07
r3d100013195	2019-12-19	2018-11-22	2021-10-05
r3d100013421	2020-09-30	2002-08-16	2022-08-16
r3d100014027	2022-11-11	2022-01-11	2022-11-20

Figure 31: Debatables between *updated_corrected* and *entryDate*

Figure 31 shows debatables between *updated_corrected* and *entryDate* documented by 26 repositories where *updated_corrected* is smaller than *entryDate*.

updated_corrected

updated_corrected

Figure 32: updated_corrected boxplot

Min.	2002-08-16
1st Qu.	2018-12-07
Median	2020-07-31
3rd Qu.	2022-02-09
Max.	2022-11-25

Figure 33: updated_corrected table

Figure 32 and 33 show the analysis for *updated_corrected* with mean and interquartile range in box plot and table format.

dif_update_last

Figure 34: dif_update_last boxpot

Min.	0 days
1st Qu.	0 days
Median	10 days
3rd Qu.	737 days
Max.	7305 days

Figure 35: dif_update_last table

From 1495 12 (0.8%) are missing an *updated* value for size (see *updated_quality*). Figure 34 shows *dif_update_last* as the temporal distance between *updated_corrected* and *lastUpdate* with mean and interquartile range in box plot and table format.

4.2. Case Study

The results of the case study can be found in appendix A.

5. Discussion

5.1. Q1

An initial objective of the project was to identify for what semantic concepts the size property is being used. One basic finding was that only half of all 3037 repositories in re3data (49.2%) have a value for size. The frequency of multiple units per repository shows that very many repositories (2405) have only one unit, but the field is also used to represent several, once up to 16 units. It should be noted here that the units can also refer to or depend on each other (see *size_non_unit_type*), and herewith of course the semantic complexity grows. If the size is set, it can be abstractly narrowed down in three dimensions, *size_unit_type*, *size_unit_discipline*, *size_unit_content*, based on the given units. For all three dimensions, the reasons for repositories that have a size but no type, discipline or content lie in the complete absence or inconclusiveness of a semantic unit. However; this will be dealt with in the area of size quality (Q2). Looking at type, only 77 repositories contain pure or mixed values on volume (bytes). It is somewhat surprising that information in this form exists here at all, as the information is not permissible from a schema point of view. All other values given were quantitative units, as expected. The approach to the units given via the discipline has brought to light that most repositories use pure generic units (931) vs the 513 pure or mixed with disciplinary units. This result indicates a great potential for standardisation on the side of generic ones and a great complexity problem on the side of disciplinary ones. When approaching the content to which the unit refers, it can be seen that pure neutral units are used for the larger part (884) that do not give us any clues.

However, for the 599 that have information on data content, it is so manifold and elusive that it could only be recorded as “other” in the first analysis. The exemplary approach to individual units has shown that various new content types can be assigned: abstract, file, method, no-data (nodata) and physical. Often a clear differentiation between the content types was not possible, e.g. if something digital or physical is counted: e.g. “mouse samples”. That is also true for abstract units such as “models” that can be file-orientated at the same time. The usefulness of counting text-based file types (e.g. “publications”) can be questioned when it is actually about research data. Other things of a statistical nature are also counted, which in the narrower sense have even less to do with research data (e.g. “hits each month”). References to a research method provide exciting information (e.g. “multi-centric studies”) as these are not explicitly covered in the re3data schema. On the other hand, the content aspects mentioned are all presented in a very unstructured and inconsistent form. So even if they are useful, a standardisation between them seems far fetched. In relation to RDA (see chapter 2.5), type of content and type of media seem most comparable to *size_unit_content*. Type of format and modes of issuance are defined in the case of repositories as digital data in a continuous form, even though *size_unit_content_other* has set out the problem with counting physical units.

Taking a closer look at the generic/neutral units, the mapping to one of the granularity concepts mentioned in chapter 2.3. produced interesting results. The unit “dataset” is already somewhat more widespread (10.3% of the units) and allows a comparison between the repositories, at least in theory. However, the significance is limited since standardisation of dataset (and thus of granularity) is not firmly defined either; see “12,148,116 datasets” as the maximum. Datasets can be packed and structured differently, e.g. with regard to deposit in a generic or subject-specific repository. Nevertheless, the counting is not entirely without significance. The six repositories with one dataset show that the registration policy of re3data also enables the inclusion of small or newly emerged repositories. Here, a chicken-and-egg problem arises: the entry in re3data can increase visibility and reuse, but a few datasets are needed to check the repository and examine its vitality for inclusion.

The comparison between the dimension *size_unit_discipline* and *size_unit_content* has shown a very strong correlation (0.88) between generic and neutral, e.g. “datasets”. Same goes slightly moderated for disciplinary and other (0.77), e.g. “essential non-coding sequences”. This is understandable since disciplinary focus and disciplinary content often but not always go hand in hand. Counterexamples would be “images” (discipline:generic but content:other) or “atmospheric data” (discipline:disciplinary but content:neutral). Overall the heterogeneity of repositories outlined in chapter 2.1. is thus related to the diversity of the size property presented here. Surprisingly, sizes on data level (metadata standards) mentioned in chapter 3.4. do not provide a structured description of these. It should also be noted that re3data already captures information on the disciplinarity of a repository (*type* and *subject*) and the repository’s content (*contentType*). Regarding the information that is not strictly unit-orientated, it can be seen that most effort goes into providing more accuracy for the unit (13%) or relating the units to each other as part-of-information (5.6%). Smaller effort goes into expanding the detail level (1.3%) (e.g. “meteorological stations throughout Southeast Asia”) or providing oversight over the collection (0.7%).

The attribute *providerType* is rather vaguely defined, and the physical holding is more decisive than anything else. On the other hand, the distinction between data and metadata can often only be made in a local context. For example, a portal (service provider) may harvest data from another repository, but it is impossible to tell whether this is research data or its metadata. The 74% (dataProvider, serviceProvider and empty) should therefore give us no clue about that. In a stricter sense, neither are the (26%) dataProvider and serviceProvider, but for this combination, the interpretation is closer that local full-text data are available and supplemented with references (metadata) via external full-text data. However, the mentioned part-of-information or other peculiarities have not indicated a widespread division into full text and non-full text (e.g. “~100 datasets with metadata, of which some contain several subsets.”).

The Case Study could only make a small contribution to this research question but has confirmed the excesses of disciplinary information, which may be even greater in the original sources (PeanutBase, ICSD). The problem of the occurrence of text units (BUIR, ICSD) could also be illustrated and will be discussed in Q2.

5.2. Q2

This study found several quality issues when assessing the size property and related fields. It seems not wise to store size information in other fields such as *description* or *remarks*. Even the rough estimate of candidates 35.6% for *description* and 19.9% for *remarks* gives reason for caution. This information needs to be updated individually and can include outdated values. Size is rapidly changing and hard to structure, and maintaining redundant values manually does not contribute to quality. As mentioned, only half of all 3037 repositories in re3data (49.2%) have a value for size, which is undeniably a quality problem. This is particularly serious in the case of similar sources, which are sometimes listed with and sometimes without size, e.g. open data portals such as Open Data Catalogue - City of Lethbridge (r3d100012976) vs Open Data Markham (r3d100014054). This study could not generate any comprehensive statements for the blank values. However, the case study showed that size information could be determined for two repositories that do not yet have a value: clear values for BUIR, harder to capture values for PeanutBase. Although the lack of values is not a systematic error between the schema version and the running service, as mentioned in chapter 2.4, the number still seems very high and needs further investigation. On the other hand, it can be considered to make the field mandatory; compare the rather facultative occurrence of size in RDA (see chapter 2.5). This would prevent it from being forgotten for prioritisation reasons. Although the size field fulfils the criterion of completeness in the sense of an extensive description, its informative value is limited if no such value exists for half of the repositories. The mentioned diversity of units in Q1 contradicts the quality standards of logical consistency and coherence.

The ICSD is a good example of how a lot of size information is stored that contains syntactical errors as well as size related information (accuracy, part-of-information, detail) and inflates the field and makes accessibility difficult. But, since *size_non_unit_type* values are not provided consistently for all values, the meaningfulness is limited. One can doubt whether a quantification of the size in form of accuracy offers any added value. On a formal level, quantors are not standardized (e.g. “+”, “more than”), and in terms of content, it seems not necessary to highlight the vagueness of the value. The part-of-information offers semantic added value, but at the price that the units do not stand on their own. RDA also allows the counting of subunits, albeit in a more structured way (see chapter 2.5). At the same time, things are counted in re3data that are not always the data products of the repository but rather belong to the background understanding (“312.221 images featuring 27.850 subjects from

2.586 photographers”). As mentioned in the methodology, in a strict sense these part-of-relations would also have to be evaluated as syntax errors. The omittable information does not offer any additional value. Expansion of the units detail level or the oversight as entirety (e.g. “CLEA Lower Chamber Elections Archive: 1.900 elections from 170 countries; CLEA Upper Chamber Elections Archive: 181 elections from 24 countries”) over the collection occurs rarely and is there generating heterogonous quality. If one looks at size quality in the narrower sense, the first thing that stands out is that 12.4% of the repositories have problems in this respect. Many errors revolve around formal circumstances: syntax errors (e.g. separation), dot errors (e.g. missing, wrong position, instead of comma), number errors (e.g. natural language number), comma errors (e.g. missing, wrong position, instead of dot), orthographic error, that relate to the criterion accuracy. A standard abbreviation cannot be easily determined, but ambiguity is present in the example “7.525 TB Cases”: terabyte vs tuberculosis. Issues with the unit's interpretability also weigh heavily, such as semantic errors, distribution errors, language errors or ranges (see examples in Q3.2). The error combinations seem negligible, although they can also amplify the quality problems per repository.

The 40 repositories that have quality issues with size *updated* seem few but carry essential characteristics for the occurrence of errors in a temporal sense (see quality criterion timeliness) and can call into question the value of the size field altogether. The problem of the obsolescence of the size field exists regardless. 25% of the repositories have no temporal distance between an update of size and an update of the whole record. For another 25% and up to the median, the distance is smaller than 10. For 75% of the repositories, the value rises to below 737 days, and the last 25% lead to a maximum of 7305 days. This means that the size is usually checked if (!) the record is changed. The rest can not be clearly interpreted, as the size date may also have been revised but not changed (see Q 3.2), but a tendency for the data to become obsolete is discernible. If we look at the case studies, we find that those with an existing size, and thus an *updated* value, are very current. That is *updated* (“2022-04-28”) in relation to *lastUpdate* (“2022-05-02”) in the case of ICSD, and it is similar in the case of ScieneDB. However, here the total update is already over a year old (“2021-09-03”) and the size may have changed considerably, especially in the case of a rather generic repository. In the case of ICSD, one can see how the size information has changed over time: the section stored in re3data is not given on the website in this way but has probably been corrected again and again over time with regard to the size numbers. This is also shown by the internal screenshot of the last change request. The changes over time are also visible on the old page from 2016 or the other sources. In the case of ScienceDB, older site versions, such as 2020, show display errors in the archive website version and offer no additional information. Apparently, the distinction between public and private (save) datasets was abandoned in the last change request, with the autopsy again distinguishing between open and deposited datasets.

The case study also revealed quality issues behind the existing units. In the case of BUIR, it is not clear if the units represent the total amount of records (“45224”) in the repository of just the two (research data) datasets. Also, it is difficult for a cataloguer to distinguish between “15625 Scholarly Publications” and “29599 University Library”. As mentioned in Q1 the *providerType* is not helpful for that distinction. One would have to decide whether only the full-text records are counted or not, but in contrast to OpenDOAR, both kinds are not counted simultaneously. As discussed in chapter 2.3. lack of distinguishment between full text and metadata could lead to high numbers for the count of items in text repositories. As of now, the problem seems less virulent for research data repositories. With BUIR, there are also major differences between the GUI and API specifications for size (“45224” vs „31664“). ScienceDB shows how much the current value for datasets can differ from that in re3data (factor 13). It is impossible to clarify whether there is an error or a major change, but together with the ScienceDB publication, it speaks for rapid growth. This violates the criterion of accuracy. The volume information at ScienceDB illustrates the problems with dots and comma separation: “34.002 GB” data is stored in re3data. Here it is unclear whether 34 TB or 34 GB is meant. The website information “299.158 +GB” should be assumed to mean 299.158 GB.

The credibility of the size information (provenance) is underlined in ICSD and ScienceDB by the fact that the sender of the last change request comes from the repository provider itself.

5.3. Q3.1

To improve the quality of the size property, automated and intellectual measures can be applied. The first step is to examine the possibilities for automation, which can also be a first step towards machine readability. One option would be to take over the data concerning size from another source. OpenDOAR offers that option but is, as of now, only assigned to 1.4% of re3data records. As shown in the BUIR case study for an institutional repository, the size value is retrievable, even if it differs from the values in the GUI. For a systematic approach, all values should be checked in advance for a possible assignment. At first glance, the other registry identifiers (35.3%) do not offer such possibilities. However, this would have to be examined in more detail, as would a systematic comparison of all re3data records with OpenDOAR in order to increase the number of matches if necessary. Tapping the size directly from the repository software (e.g. RADAR, Dataverse) would be another approach. This still needs to be implemented and would be highly experimental. In the case of a homogeneous source (i.e. Dataverse), an attempt can also be made to form media type (MIME) clusters within it, which works particularly well for single-type metadata (Trisovic, 2022).

Less than 20% of the records use a standard repository software, of which most have standardised APIs to retrieve size. Looking at API automation in general, 53.4% of repositories offer the theoretical possibility. For example, 7.8% use well-standardised OAI PMH protocols, which is also shown in the

BUIR and ScienceDB case study. Although, especially for ScienceDB, the value of 3921 datasets is very different from the GUI (“6,682,294 results” or “398,360 datasets”) and needs further investigation. Whether the widespread REST protocol (17.3%) is easy to query across multiple repositories is open to question. In the case of PeanutBase the pseudo API (FTP) offers little automatable size information. Some APIs of ICSD and ScienceDB are not even listed in re3data. However, in the case of ICSD, easily retrievable size information is probably not available here, as the restful API is part of the licence package and is offered specifically for large amounts of data; ScienceDBs APIs offer the same small value as DataCite (see following). 44.6% of the repositories use a *pidSystem*, thus opening up the theoretical possibility of obtaining data on size. In the case of *pidSystem* DOI (29.8% DOI), concrete possibilities exist, at least for DataCite DOIs. However, the necessary mapping between re3dataIDs and DataCite client IDs is far from complete: “Currently, only 206 (as of April 13th, 2021) repositories indexed in re3data have a DataCite client ID; therefore, this approach would be limited to a small number of repositories indexed in re3data (7.73%)” (re3data COREF, 2022). As with OpenDOAR, however, systematic matching could increase the number. The ScienceDB case study has provided proof-of-concept for DataCite, although the value of 3,927 datasets is again different from the GUI.

In the case of certified repositories, it could be asked whether there are plans to record such information in a structured way in the future (e.g. CTS). In that case, it could also be adopted. The distribution of *metadataStandardName* shows that for 48% of the repositories, there is no metadata standard from which information on size could be harvested. Information could be stored for the selected metadata standards DataCite (22.8%) and ISO 19115 (5%). However, as described in chapter 2.4, there is also no structured information for DataCite, and only volume information would be available for ISO. Since both fields are optional, it is still not certain how often this information actually exists. One could investigate this harvesting possibility in the case of ScienceDB and check how often size values are present at the dataset level and how they can be used in a granularity sense. DataCite's metadata standard is not listed on re3data in that case.

The locations in re3data (*description*, *remarks*) mentioned in Q2, in which size information is or can be stored, could be checked automatically, i.e. once systematically and with each new entry or entry change. The (50.8%) records must have a size attribute to be checked by a machine, but security prompts for future entries or changes can prevent the size attribute from being forgotten in contrast to not being found. Since size in volume format (bytes) is not covered by the re3data schema, it should be sorted out automatically when entered. The large variety of units, demonstrated by *size_unit_discipline* and *size_unit_content*, can only be automated to a limited extent. One possibility would be to standardise generic and neutral units, for example, through a field test with “datasets”. Disciplinary and other units could achieve a higher degree of standardisation through auto-completion.

It should be noted here that long-established library models, represented here by RDA or IFLA-LRM (see chapter 2.5), also contain no references to controlled units. Furthermore, the question would arise whether the units should be formally fixed in the schema or only downstream in the backend. If it is considered important to have values outside the size number and size unit (*size_non_unit_type*), these should be stored in an extra size subfield. A uniform, standardised set of quantifiers or part-of-relations can lead to more standardisation but also more complexity. Detailed unit information outside the unit interferes with automated processing and must therefore be classified as poor quality.

In order to solve the problems detected in *size_quality*, several measures can be applied. The formal errors mentioned: syntax errors, dot errors, comma errors, number errors and orthographic errors can be well reduced automatically. First, the size field should be divided into *size_number* and *size_unit* subfields, allowing a rough check of numeric and alphabetic values. Compare the IFLA-LRM, which does not define any explicit sub-attributes in the abstract but distinguishes between type of extent, number and measurement unit in the scope notes. These can be expressed in the example realisations by subfields to “sub-extents”. Alternatively, the previous separation syntax can be retained (“;”), which must then be automatically validated before saving. Thousands separators should not be entered in the data but only generated for the display of size. An automated spell check can help against spelling errors. In the case of comma and dot errors, one has to decide in favour of a decimal separator, which can also be checked automatically. Errors concerning the interpretability of the unit (semantic errors, distribution errors, language errors or ranges) are not easy to automate. Only the complete absence of units and the use of non-English language can be dealt with in this way. In the case of interpretation of the size as upload limit (“Current size limit is 2 GB per file and 20 GB per a single dataset”) can be automated little, because only 30.2% can be excluded with *dataUploadType* closed. ScienceDB, for example, states no limit on their FAQ regarding upload size. The quality of the *updated* field can be increased by assigning the field only in combination with a filled size field and by automatically time stamping the field when the size property is entered or changed. This is also supported by the re3data indexing handbook and by the 4 cases in which *updated* is incorrectly greater than *lastUpdate*. If this is not possible, the entries can still be checked for validity with regard to a date format with plausible content and in relation to *lastUpdate*. However, it should generally be checked whether the dating of a single field is in harmony with the dating of the whole record. Since size data can naturally become outdated quickly, automatic updates with either daily or weekly updates are preferred. There are also opportunities for automation in re3data’s internal area. Changes in property size should be tracked to make them traceable over time. This would also benefit the quality criterion of provenance. If one thinks one step further, experimental automations can be used to support the indexer, e.g. a comparison of the *size_unit* with *type*, *contentType* or *subject*, *keyword* of the repository. Automation

also makes sense when checking the credibility of the size information. A modified trust model is needed that locates the human or technical source of the data.

5.4. Q3.2

The aforementioned automations must be supplemented in many places by intellectual measures. A large area of repositories cannot be automated at all in terms of size and size quality. For all automated measures mentioned above, which cannot be realised, the corresponding intellectual counterpart applies (e.g. sorting out volume data or general awareness of quality assurance). In the following, only rather new measures are mentioned. A first measure would be to critically examine the exceptionally high proportion of no size (50.8%), either continuously during routine checks or systematically. For repositories where the GUI should not be freely accessible (21 offer closed access, and 147 provide restricted access) and no accessible API should exist, the same issues for size apply as for all other fields. If available, other sources such as publications (PeanutBase, ICSD) or certification documents (e.g. CTS for r3d100013195) can be used, whereby the topicality of the information must be taken into account. At PeanutBase, parts of the content could also be available at other repositories (NCBI GEO, Array Express and Seq Read Archive) where better-prepared size information can exist. Here too, however, the disciplinary expertise should not be underestimated. Downloading and calculating the size on the editor's side seems impractical (PeanutBase). A stricter source hierarchy is not expedient, given the diversity of repositories. Nevertheless, the main page or empty search page has a certain importance: be it to decide in case of number conflicts (BUIR) or to decide whether to include a size at all in case of exuberant disciplinary content (PeanutBase).

The BUIR case has shown that there can be a difference between the research data and the counted units in re3data. In a narrower sense, there are only two datasets of research data. However, not every repository offers the possibility to filter by file type, and other types may contain research data (e.g. video). The same applies to counting non-full-text data. The 978 (32.2%) repositories with *enhancedPublication* can give a slight hint if textual data exists. In BUIR, types would be ascertainable (even if there are none), but not every repository also offers corresponding faceting options. In the case of ScienceDB, the data typing is similarly inconclusive; a focus on "dataset (398,360)", for example, would exclude the exorbitantly high number of "others (4,251,723)". This repository further distinguishes between public and non-public data ("6,682,294 Open datasets; 6,814,785 Deposited datasets").

In the case of non-standardizable units, great attention is required on the part of the indexer. As in classical cataloguing, only an autopsy can be decisive. However, in the case of PeanutBase this information is spread over many sub-sources and is almost impossible to use without expertise, so a blank size value may be justified. Counting units or files by hand, as is theoretically possible with

PeanutBase (at least for parts), does not seem practical; the repository should directly present the size number and unit. In the case of the ICSD, the size information is presented more clearly, albeit in abundance. A complexity reduction rule can help here so that only the total value “272.000 crystal structures”, which is also highlighted by the website (without the “>”), can be recorded. Here, no-data units or text units would also be omitted. On the other hand, it can be observed here that resources with restricted databaseAccess can run into difficulties: the landing page does not directly provide any size information, and the search is only possible from an approved IP address, even if it cannot be sent as an empty search. The dot/comma problem mentioned in Q2 needs the highest attention from the indexer; see ScienceDB.

In the temporal analysis between *updated_corrected* and *entryDate (dif_update_last)*, quality problems cannot be solved automatically: The 26 repositories where *updated_corrected* is smaller than *entryDate* may have other reasons besides errors: the extreme case 2002-08-16 suggests that this date was explicitly mentioned on the website and not that the date was on the side of re3data. PeanutBase offers time information for some parts of their size information (“Last Update: May 25, 2021”). Clarifying the exact field definition in the schema and in the indexing rules can help here. Manual update cycles cannot be kept at the same level as automatic ones and must fit into general check-ups routines, such as every record once a year.

When obtaining values from *size_non_unit_type*, all values that are not automated must be assigned consistently; this applies to values from accuracy or the part-of-information. Only detail and omissible content can be left out without greater risk. Entirety is more difficult to structure in conformity with quality. Since *size_number* and *size_unit* have shown that several sizes exist, one can consider making the size field repeatable. As already mentioned, the formal *size_quality* errors should be fixed automatically. Errors concerning the interpretability of the unit (semantic errors, distribution errors, language errors or ranges) must be checked intellectually and may be more severe. For semantic errors, the units must be critically questioned, e.g. “1 mm or Total number of data: 5,250,957”. Distribution errors (e.g. “143 projects; 36 with open access content”) must be resolved so that the units can stand for themselves, see also in the previous section on entirety. Whether to include size ranges is not easy to answer. In the course of this work, it was forcibly normalised to obtain comparability for natural language numbers: “thousands of Affymetrix GeneChip datasets = 1000-9000 datasets”. RDA allows an estimation of the number of units in comparison. However, there are not many cases where this would be of any importance. An increase of the review process for every size change can, after applying the individual measures mentioned, further improve the quality. However, this does not seem appropriate for a property with priority 3, but systematic checks at certain intervals could help. Furthermore, the mentioned rule to refer to the source of the size in the *remarksIntern*

was not applied in the case of ICSD and ScienceDB. The rule is grounded in the goal of traceability of information but creates a lot of complexity (think of a revision of the repository website). However, this would guarantee the quality criterion of provenance.

Until a technical check of the trustworthiness of the source of the size (and its change) is determined, the indexer has to decide on the basis of email domains or personal research (ICSD, ScienceDB). From the experience of the re3data editorial team in responding to contact requests, the following points can be noted regarding size: confusion with the limit for data upload, references to formal errors (separators), questions about the inclusion of further entities such as journals, doubts about manual updates and interest in storage values for comparisons.

6. Conclusion

This work cannot provide a conclusive answer to the overall problem but can be seen as a step towards a better understanding. The following limitations should be noted. Although the research design already combines different methods, the integration of machine learning (e.g. clustering) in the area of units (especially *size_content_type_other*) and a more detailed multivariate analysis could lead to further results. As already mentioned, there is an exceptionally high proportion of repositories with no size, which would have to be investigated specifically. Combining new typed properties that resemble existing properties such as (e.g. *type* and *size_unit_discipline* or *contentType* and *size_unit_content*) seem promising to detect possible overlap or potential for new properties are a desiderate. Furthermore, it could be fruitful even to experiment with emerging technologies such as ChatGTP (Garza, 2023). The operationalisation of quality dimensions in terms of measurability depends on the respective environment, for example (Király, 2019, p. 78). No strict measurement and mapping on quality dimensions was done for this rather explorative work. However, developing suitable and measurable indicators could be the next step. For studies of the change in size, the re3data database in SQL format could be used. In this way, editorial comments and technical value changes could be used to at least determine how often size values were changed. The problem of shutdown repositories was not dealt with in depth in this work since a clean modelling (see *endDate* and *description*) of this status and the verifiability is currently not available. However, as soon as comprehensive findings are available, there will also be material for research on size, e.g. does the size remain at the last status, or is it set to 0 (see r3d100010545)? Specific questions could also be directed towards research software in terms of countability, units and granularity. Extending the comparison with bibliographic concepts to a theoretical level or their empirical application in the library community could also provide further insights. All of these aspects can be seen as desiderata and, regardless of their concrete applicability to registries such as re3data, can make contributions to research on metadata indexing in continuing to capture and analyse the self-expression of size across repositories.

What conclusions can be drawn from the results listed and discussed? One possibility is to approach the problem via a decision tree together with pros and cons. In the beginning, there is the question of whether the size property should be recorded continually or at all. This thesis cannot provide an accurate answer to this question, as it requires a needs analysis for concrete use cases in the community. That resembles the biggest quality factor: a “fitness for purpose” mentioned in chapter 2.4 has not been clarified. What is needed is an outline of scenarios where the detailed specification and documentation of size really adds value for stakeholders. What we see is that comparable registries like FAIRsharing do not use any or at least no openly accessible sizes. Furthermore, current initiatives such as DRAWG, which represents at least some stakeholders in the research data infrastructure community, suggest that size should at least not be understood as a core attribute. It is

possible that the services (e.g. re3data and FAIRsharing) can also enrich each other in case of missing attributes (Wang, 2022, p. 63). However, if repositories are to be described adequately, a central concept such as size (in whatever form) is actually indispensable from a quality point of view alone (completeness). Also, it would be hard to make assertions about the landscape of repositories when the size is completely omitted, see for example the studies mentioned in chapter 2.3. regarding OpenDOAR. It remains open why there is no stronger focus on size in metadata standards. Although the size of a repository can be more than the sum of its parts, anchoring it more strongly at research data level in the sense of granularity would be essential. At the same time, one could also conclude from the absence of stricter standards that the community has no great need for a sustainable description and use of the field.

If one decides to record the size further, various measures, ranging from minimal to maximal invasive, can alleviate quality problems and should be combined in a mixture. The question of whether the semantic dimension of size is regularly included as volume/storage can be asked. Presumably, however, there is rarely more information about the total volume of the repository. The first option for general improvement would be to leave the size in its open form but in an optimised way. The selection of the most suitable information source for size is additionally important, and must be generalised in advance via a defined subset in the case of automation and determined on the basis of the individual case together with the indexing rules in the case of intellectual indexing. Automatic quality checks, in the sense of a co-pilot for the cataloguer, can mitigate existing problems such as syntax checks, time stamps and internal logical dependencies. In addition, the intellectual measures can be improved. Clarification of the indexing rules and consistent application of them as well as reduction of complexity, are decisive for this. All of the changes mentioned would preserve most diversity of the size and thus benefit the user and would produce better structured data with fewer errors. At the same time, the personnel effort involved is high and can even be higher than it is now.

The field would have to be split into subfields for *size_number* and *size_unit* and made repeatable. For the complete preservation of the current information, even a relation between the *size_number* and *size_unit* combinations would be necessary, which would greatly increase the complexity of the entire field. Furthermore, size values should be automatically retrieved from all addressed sources that are available per repository: other registries, PID providers and APIs (and maybe also technologies such as web scraping). Certainly, no complete solution is possible here, but one could start with individual pioneer projects: e.g. OAI-PMH or DataCite client IDs. A sound trust model is important for this. The sources must be checked in advance and found to be of high enough quality for the selected repositories. Manual changes should then no longer be possible for editors or only in exceptional cases. The advantages are faster availability of data and guaranteed timeliness, but the technical effort

increases. The above intellectual measures apply for all repositories that do not offer automation options. Here, too, the part for the trust model must be developed. A registration system for repository operators or certified community curators can create transparency and also promote the participation character inherent in re3data as an initiative. Attempting to standardise unit values can provide valuable information about the concept of size and bring together researchers and research infrastructure representatives. In contrast, the correct measure of a disciplinary unit must be decided ultimately by the community. This statement is also covered by the quality criterion conformance to expectations (see chapter 2.5).

Qualitative differences can arise when combining the different measures, e.g. automatic, daily update of the size via API and intellectual check-up once a year. This requires further research also for other properties and their indexing priority, but since data sets can be maintained differently through community change requests, a mixed situation remains. The editorial team can continue to provide basic curation. A rather exotic approach would be to count only repositories that have been definitively closed. This can then be compared more with the bibliographic description tradition. Although the library data world in particular is characterised by a long tradition of standardisation, something can be adopted here in terms of general indexing rules. What is crucial, however, is the feedback between the stakeholders there (e.g. publishers), which still needs to be more mature in the relatively young research infrastructure and is made more difficult by the strong subject-specific component. The value of re3data and, in particular, the size attribute also depends mainly on how this information is or can be used. (Fritze, 2017, p. 10) shows that traditional issues of usability evaluation can be transferred to non-commercial services such as re3data. Current GUI improvements of size after a consolidation of the property could be: analysis of search queries and, e.g. inferences about the units, providing search suggestions, e.g. for the units, display of size's schema definition and experimental facets such as visual controllers to explore numeric scales of size or adaption of the vitality of repository in the icon system, which also could include a (change of) size component.

Finally, the following concluding observations can be considered for further reflection and can be used as an *ex negativo* argumentation for size. The used values of re3data's properties, especially when they include standards such as in the metadata property, can be of help to designers of new repositories to avoid metadata-related problems (Kim & Choi, 2017, p. 46). Furthermore, re3data's continuously improving schema itself, including size and related properties, can give valuable insights for all research data stakeholders, e.g. repository creators and operators (Schabinger, 2014, p. 64). Almost all the initiatives mentioned in chapter 2.2.4. place great emphasis on openness and user-centeredness. It would lead to a skewed position if size was not taken into account in any way. because it is precisely one of the users first entry points for assessing new repository platforms. That includes the fact, that

size (and granularity) can change over time and be an indicator of vitality of a repository. Although the rule “class instead of mass” is certainly true most of the time, there is no denying that large repositories like Zenodo, where the size is also constantly growing, enjoy a certain importance in the community. In contrast, the repository Pangaea (r3d100010134), which is relevant in disciplinary terms, has not recorded any size in re3data. It must be noted that depositor needs in granularity may vary from the one discovering researchers have, not mentioning other stakeholders. Also, individual size values can be interpreted individually or together with other attributes of the repository, from which different conclusions can be drawn, e.g. one national study vs one single study in a specific domain. The size information can also be more complex such as how the repository deals with size and granularity, e.g. are there research services below dataset level? Is the data coming from an Electronic Lab Notebook (ELN)? Finally, as a thought experiment: would it not be a loss of information if one did not know how big re3data itself is?

Looking at current emerging topics, the concept of FAIR Digital Objects (FDO) seems of great importance. Coming from RDA initiatives, it presents an abstract technology-independent concept in applying the FAIR principles to digital objects, linking policies and technical abstractions, and striking out a coupling between metadata, data and persistent identifiers. FDOs should also be the standard way data is represented in repositories (Schwardmann, 2020) and could also help bridge the interoperability gap since overall API standardisation is not likely. In a more concrete implementation, the FAIR Digital Object Framework touches on mentioned topics like granularity (e.g. collections) and heavily relies on typed characteristics of data (Bonino da Silva Santos, 2022), which can be size-like information and thus the concept of size may be necessary for linked data services. Big PID technologies such as DOIs can be seen as entry points to other granularity levels, providing information for the operations that can be done with the objects, e.g. images can be decreased in resolution.

Regarding the metric part of size, the “belief in numbers” continues to pervade the science system. Nevertheless, there are critical discussions by funders themselves noticing a negative impact on replication (German Research Foundation, 2017, p. 4) or integrated initiatives capturing dataset complexities (Lowenberg et al., 2019, p. 22). In conclusion, the saying “Not everything that can be counted counts, and not everything that counts can be counted” (Cameron, 1963, p. 13) may not be that far from the truth.

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Affidavit

FACHHOCHSCHULE POTSDAM
Fachbereich Informationswissenschaften
Studiengang Digitales Datenmanagement (DDM)
der Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin (HU Berlin) und der Fachhochschule Potsdam (FHP)

Eidesstattliche Erklärung zur Masterarbeit

Auf der letzten Seite der Abschlussarbeit ist auf der Grundlage von § 20 Abs. 10 Rahmenordnung für Studium und Prüfungen der Fachhochschule Potsdam folgende Erklärung abzugeben und mit Datum und eigenhändiger Unterschrift zu versehen:

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und		
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• die eingereichten PDF-Dateien mit den Printexemplaren identisch sind.		
Helmsheim	25.02.2023	
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Ort	Datum	Unterschrift

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Es wird darauf hingewiesen, dass der Verstoß gegen die Angaben in der eidesstaatliche Versicherung nicht nur einen Täuschungsversuch im Sinne von § 28 Rahmenordnung für Studium und Prüfungen der Fachhochschule Potsdam darstellt, sondern zugleich eine falsche Versicherung an Eides Statt gemäß § 156 Strafgesetzbuch: Wer vor einer zur Abnahme einer Versicherung an Eides Statt zuständigen Behörde eine solche Versicherung falsch abgibt oder unter Berufung auf eine solche Versicherung falsch aussagt, wird mit Freiheitsstrafe bis zu drei Jahren oder mit Geldstrafe bestraft.

Appendix A

Case Study of Repositories

Table of Contents

Bilkent University Institutional Repository (BUIR)	II
Overview	II
Date of Retrieval.....	IV
GUI.....	IV
API	VI
Other Sources.....	VI
PeanutBase.....	VII
Overview	VII
Date of Retrieval.....	IX
GUI.....	IX
API	XII
Other Sources.....	XII
Inorganic Crystal Structure Database (ICSD).....	XIII
Overview	XIII
Date of Retrieval.....	XV
GUI.....	XV
API	XVIII
Other Sources.....	XVIII
Internal.....	XVIII
ScienceDB.....	XIX
Overview	XIX
Date of Retrieval.....	XXI
GUI.....	XXI
API	XXII
Other Sources.....	XXIII
Internal.....	XXIII

Bilkent University Institutional Repository (BUIR)

Overview

BUIR represents a common Institutional repository with standard software (DSpace). It offers other languages besides English (Turkish) and multidisciplinary content with broad content types. No size values are present but a repositoryIdentifier with OpenDOAR-ID and an API with widespread technology (OAI). It is a data provider but also offers the thinking space for being a service provider with the facet to full text yes/no. It was recorded more recently (2020), with the entry not updated since the beginning of 2021.

re3data.orgIdentifier	r3d100013352
repositoryName	Bilkent University Institutional Repository
repositoryURL	http://repository.bilkent.edu.tr/
repositoryIdentifier	OpenDOAR:3533
description	This site provides access to the research output of the institution. The interface is available in English. Users may set up email or RSS feeds to be alerted to new content.
type	institutional
size	
size_number	
size_unit	
size_unit_type	
size_unit_discipline	
size_unit_content	
size_non_unit_type	
size_quality	
updated	
updated_corrected	
updated_quality	
startDate	
endDate	
repositoryLanguage	eng tur
subjects	1 Humanities and Social Sciences 103 Fine Arts, Music, Theatre and Media Studies 10301 Art History 109 Education Sciences 10902 Research on Teaching, Learning and Training 11 Humanities 111 Social Sciences 11104 Political Science 112 Economics 11204 Business Administration 12 Social and Behavioural Sciences 2 Life Sciences 201 Basic Biological and Medical Research

	20107 Bioinformatics and Theoretical Biology 21 Biology 3 Natural Sciences 301 Molecular Chemistry 31 Chemistry 33 Mathematics 4 Engineering Sciences 43 Materials Science and Engineering 44 Computer Science, Electrical and System Engineering
contentType	Audiovisual data Databases Images Plain text Scientific and statistical data formats Structured text
providerType	dataProvider
keyword	IEEE computer science economics engineering history materials science multidisciplinary nanotechnology
databaseAccessType	open
dataUploadType	restricted
softwareName	DSpace
api	http://repository.bilkent.edu.tr/oai/request?verb=Identify
apiType	OAI-PMH
pidSystem	
enhancedPublication	
certificate	
metadataStandardName	Dublin Core
remarks	
entryDate	08.06.2020
lastUpdate	08.02.2021

Date of Retrieval

17.12.2022

GUI

Landing page

- “Scholarly Publications 15625
University Library 29599”
[Total calculated: 45224]

Empty search

- “Anzeige der Dokumente 1-10 von 45455”¹

- “Show Advanced Filters
Has File(s): true ×
Anzeige der Dokumente 1-100 von 45224”²

- “Show Advanced Filters [Inverted]
Anzeige der Dokumente 1-100 von 231
Bereiche und Sammlungen, die Ihrer Suche entsprechen.
Accounting and Taxation [0]
Accounting Information Systems [7]
Acoustics and Underwater Technologies Research Center (BASTA) [7]
...”³

¹ <http://repository.bilkent.edu.tr/discover>

²

http://repository.bilkent.edu.tr/discover?filtertype 1=has content in original bundle&filter relational operator 1=contains&filter 1=true&submit_apply_filter=&scope=%2F&rpp=100&sort_by=score&order=desc

³

http://repository.bilkent.edu.tr/discover?rpp=100&etal=0&scope=/&group_by=none&page=3&sort_by=score &order=desc&filtertype 0=has content in original bundle&filter relational operator 0=notcontains&filter 0=true

Other sites

- “Browse by type:
 - Article [11557]
 - Biography [19]
 - Book Chapter [1114]
 - Book Draft [1]
 - Clipping [6]
 - Conference Paper [2513]
 - Cutting [17630]
 - Dataset [2] [Possible research data]
 - E-Book [2]
 - Editorial [141]
 - Erratum [15]
 - Image [935] [Possible research data]
 - Interview [2] [Possible research data]
 - Letter [348] [Possible research data]
 - Manuscript [2] [Possible research data]
 - Movie Script [56] [Possible research data]
 - Musical Score [1] [Possible research data]
 - Note [1]
 - Offprint [151]
 - Other [2] [Possible research data]
 - Paper [2]
 - Poster [1]
 - Presentation [3]
 - Proceedings Paper [2]
 - Recording, oral [1] [Possible research data]
 - Report [5]
 - Review [268]
 - Student Project [4098]
 - Supplement Non-Book [1] [Possible research data]
 - Technical Report [3]

Thesis [6331]

Video [2]

[Possible research data]

Website [1]

[Possible research data]"⁴

API

- "Results fetched 0 - 100 of 31664"⁵

Other Sources

- [API of OpenDOAR]

"metadata_record_count 31664

full_text_record_count 6686"⁶

⁴ <http://repository.bilkent.edu.tr/browse?type=type>

⁵ http://repository.bilkent.edu.tr/oai/request?verb=ListRecords&metadataPrefix=oai_dc

⁶ https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/cgi/retrieve_by_id?item-type=repository&api-key=4327452C-4EB9-11ED-846A-26233423C7BC&format=Json&identifier=3533

PeanutBase

Overview

PeanutBase is a disciplinary repository with the widespread topic of genetics that has existed for almost 10 years. It offers possibly specialized content (types) and includes software applications. It presents no size value but a repository identifier (FAIRsharing_DOI) and enhanced publications. No standard repository software, PID system and metadata standard are visible. It was recorded not recently (2017), with the entry not updated since the end of 2021.

re3data.orgIdentifier	r3d100012355
repositoryName	PeanutBase
repositoryURL	https://peanutbase.org
repositoryIdentifier	FAIRsharing_DOI:10.25504/FAIRsharing.fYFurb
description	PeanutBase is a peanut community resource providing genetic, genomic, gene function, and germplasm data to support peanut breeding and molecular research. This includes molecular markers, genetic maps, QTL data, genome assemblies, germplasm records, and traits. Data is curated from literature and submitted directly by researchers. Funding for PeanutBase is provided by the Peanut Foundation with in-kind contributions from the USDA-ARS.
type	disciplinary
size	
size_number	
size_unit	
size_unit_type	
size_unit_discipline	
size_unit_content	
size_non_unit_type	
size_quality	
updated	
updated_corrected	
updated_quality	
startDate	2013
endDate	
repositoryLanguage	eng
subjects	2 Life Sciences 202 Plant Sciences 20207 Plant Genetics 21 Biology

contentType	Archived data Databases Images Scientific and statistical data formats Software applications Standard office documents
providerType	dataProvider
keyword	Arachis Arachis durenensis Arachis hypogea Arachis ipaensis bioinformatics disease resistance genetics genomics germplasm groundnut plant breeding ploidy
databaseAccessType	open
dataUploadType	restricted
softwareName	
api	
apiType	
pidSystem	
enhancedPublication	yes
certificate	
metadataStandardName	
remarks	
entryDate	01.05.2017
lastUpdate	16.11.2021

Date of Retrieval

17.12.2022

GUI

Landing page

- [NA]

PeanutBase
Genetic and genomic data to enable more rapid crop improvement in peanut.

Contact us
Newsletter signup

Home Species Browse & Search Traits & Maps Germplasm Download Submit Data Community External Help

The Peanut Genome Browse *A. duranensis* Browse *A. ipaensis*

BLAST Sequence Search BLAT Sequence Search Keyword Search

Marker Assisted Selection QTL Search Maps

Data Store Gene & Gene Family Protein Domains

Germplasm Phenotype Data Genotype data

PeanutMine

PeanutBase is a member of the Legume Federation[®] and is partnered with the Legume Information System[®]

Click for more on PeanutBase and the Peanut Genomics Initiative ...

The peanut genome has been sequenced and analyzed as part of the **International Peanut Genome Initiative**, in order to accelerate breeding progress and get more productive, disease-resistant, stress-tolerant varieties to farmers. The two diploid progenitors have been sequenced and are available, along with predicted genes and descriptions. The genomes of the diploid progenitors have been used to help identify and assemble the similar chromosomes in cultivated peanut.

Cultivated peanut, *Arachis hypogaea*, is an allotetraploid (2n=4x=40) that contains two complete genomes, labeled the **A** and **B** genomes. *A. duranensis* (2n=2x=20) has likely contributed the **A** genome, and *A. ipaensis* has likely contributed the **B** genome. It may be helpful to remember these two associations by using the mnemonic: "A" comes before "B" and "duranensis" comes before "ipaensis".

For cultivated peanut, *Arachis hypogaea* cv. Tifrunner: [assembly](#)

For the diploid progenitor *Arachis duranensis*: [assembly](#); [annotation](#)

For the diploid progenitor *Arachis ipaensis*: [assembly](#); [annotation](#)

[More about Arachis ...](#) (Download a short review on 'Arachis duranensis, Arachis ipaensis, and the Origins of Cultivated Peanut')

Let us know if you have questions, requests, or data to contribute.

Cite PeanutBase and the peanut genomes

Cite PeanutBase
Sudhansu Dash, Ethalinda K.S. Cannon, Scott R. Kaliberer, Andrew D. Farmer and Steven B. Cannon. **PeanutBase and Other Bioinformatic Resources for Peanut** (Chapter 9.6). In **Peanuts Genetics, Processing, and Utilization**, edited by H. Thomas Stalker and Richard F. Wilson. AOCSS Press, 2016. Pages 241-252. (ISBN 9781630670392, doi:10.1016/B978-1-63067-038-2.00008-3).

Cite peanut genome
David J. Bertoli, Jerry Jenkins, Josh Clevenger, Olga Dudchenko, Dongying Gao, Guillermo Sejo, Soraya C. M. Leal-Bertoli, Longhui Ren, Andrew D. Farmer, Manish K. Pandey, Sergio S. Samoluk, Brian Abernathy, Gaurav Agarwal, Carolina Bailen-Taborca, Connor Cameron, Jacqueline Campbell, Carolina Chavarro, Annapurna Chilkini, Ye Chu, Sudhansu Dash, Moaine El Baidouri, Baozhu Guo, Wei Huang, Kyung Do Kim, Waike Korani, Sophie Lanciano, Christopher G. Lui, Marie Mirouze, Márcio C. Moretzsohn, Melanie Pham, Jin Hee Shin, Kenta Shirasawa, Senjuti Sinharoy, Avinash Sreedasyam, Nathan T. Weeks, Xinyou Zhang, Zheng Zheng, Zhi Sun, Lutz Froenicke, Erez L. Alden, Richard Michelmore, Rajeev K. Varshney, C. Corley Holbrook, Ethalinda K. S. Cannon, Brian E. Scheffler, Jane Grimwood, Peggy Ozas-Akins, Steven B. Cannon, Scott A. Jackson & Jeremy Schmutz. The genome sequence of segmental allotetraploid peanut *Arachis hypogaea*. *Nature Genetics* 51, 877–884 (2019).

Bertoli DJ, Cannon SB, Froenicke L, Huang G, Farmer AD, Cannon EK, Liu X, Gao D, Clevenger J, Dash S, Ren L, Moretzsohn MC, Shirasawa K, Huang W, Vidgal B, Abernathy B, Chu Y, Niederhuth CE, Ulme P, Araujo AC, Kozak A, Do Kim K, Burrow MD, Varshney RK, Wang X, Zhang X, Barkley N, Guimarães PM, Isobe S, Guo B, Liao B, Stalker HT, Schmitz RJ, Scheffler BE, Leal-Bertoli SC, Xun X, Jackson SA, Michelmore R, Ozas-Akins P. The genome sequences of *Arachis duranensis* and *Arachis ipaensis*, the diploid ancestors of cultivated peanut. *Nature Genetics* 48:438–446 (2016). doi: 10.1038/ng.3517. PubMed PMID: 26901068. (Cited by 6) (Nature article metrics)

This resource is being developed for U.S. and international peanut researchers and breeders, with support from The Peanut Foundation.

THE PEANUT FOUNDATION Genes@home

Feedback

Firefox_Screenshot_2022-12-17T15-23-47.569Z.png

Empty search

- [one of many complex search masks that require domain knowledge and or offer no empty search]⁷

⁷ https://peanutbase.org/keyword_search

Search genome browser

Enter terms to search for features (gene or marker names, functional descriptions, etc.) on the indicated genome. You will see the results displayed on a karyotype view of chromosomes and in a list report. You can go from there to a detailed view of the features on the genome browser.

Search term:

Examples: [lipoxygenase](#), [Glyma.03G153900.1](#), [Aradu.FM0YX](#).

Species: A. duranensis

Firefox_Screenshot_2022-12-17T15-36-13.729Z.png

- “146959 genes”⁸
- [countable]⁹

Organism	Marker	Alt names used on maps
Arachis duranensis	GM10	
Arachis duranensis	GM1001	
Arachis duranensis	GM1013	
Arachis duranensis	GM1018	
Arachis duranensis	GM1023	
Arachis duranensis	GM1030	
Arachis duranensis	GM1034	
Arachis duranensis	GM1035	
Arachis duranensis	GM1045	
Arachis duranensis	GM1048	
Arachis duranensis	GM1053	
Arachis duranensis	GM1065	
Arachis duranensis	GM1069	
Arachis duranensis	GM1070	
Arachis duranensis	GM1073	
Arachis duranensis	GM1075	
Arachis duranensis	GM1076	
Arachis duranensis	GM1084	
Arachis duranensis	GM1085	
Arachis duranensis	GM1092	
Arachis duranensis	GM1096	
Arachis duranensis	GM1107	
Arachis duranensis	GM1108	
Arachis duranensis	GM1111	
Arachis duranensis	GM1114	

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 ... next » last »

Firefox_Screenshot_2022-12-17T15-38-12.571Z.png

- “Total QTL in PeanutBase: 489”¹⁰

⁸ <https://peanutbase.org/search/gene>

⁹ <https://peanutbase.org/search/marker>

¹⁰ <https://peanutbase.org/search/qt/>

Other sites

- “The genus *Arachis* contains about 70 species”¹¹
- “2 Studies
32 Phenotypes total
32 Phenotypes published
Last Update: May 25, 2021”¹²
- [countable, but no context information]¹³
- “*Arachis* germplasm image collection: Image collection contains ~2000 images from the USDA-ARS germplasm collection in Griffin, GA.”¹⁴
- “The assembly size is 2,556 Mbp, which we estimate to span more than 99% of the actually genome. The scaffold N50 (a measure of the assembly contiguity) is 135.2 MB (the scale of the complete peanut chromosomes). A total of 48.25x of PACBIO sequence (avg. read length of 11,525) was used to generate the initial assembly, which was subsequently polished using Illumina sequences and ARROW. Homozygous SNPs and INDELS were corrected in the release sequence using ~40x of illumina reads (2x250, 800bp insert, library ID ICIH and ICID). Synteny with the diploid *A. duranensis* and *A. ipaensis*, along with 1 genetic map and 2 synthetic maps (provided by David Bertioli) were used to identify misjoins in the raw assembly. The resulting assembly was then scaffolded using HiC data. Post scaffolding, 6 additional breaks were made to resolve misjoins introduced during the scaffolding procedure. The original sequences were combined with the duplicated tetrasomic regions and joined together using 26 joins to create the 20 *A. hypogaea* chromosomes. During the construction of the chromosomes, all 500bp scaffolded gaps were converted to 1,000 bp gaps, and the map joins that were added consisted of 10,000 bp gaps. Chromosomes were numbered as Arahy.01-Arahy.20, where the A genome is represented as Arahy.01-Arahy.10 and the B genome is represented as Arahy.11-Arahy.20. 99.3% of the assembled sequence is contained in the chromosomes.”¹⁵

¹¹ <https://peanutbase.org/species>

¹² <https://arachispheno.peanutbase.org/>

¹³ <https://peanutbase.org/chado/featuremap>

¹⁴ <https://peanutbase.org/help>

¹⁵ https://peanutbase.org/peanut_genome

API

- [FTP]¹⁶

Firefox_Screenshot_2022-12-17T15-43-10.891Z.png

- [Download]

Firefox_Screenshot_2022-12-17T15-46-11.321Z.png

Other Sources

- [publication 2016]

“PeanutBase contained 12 genetic maps in electronic form, and genetic locations of traits of interest (QTLs), ranging from disease resistance to architecture and abiotic stress characteristics that are curated from the literature. There are currently several 100 genetically mapped traits available at the website, and this count is increasing as new QTL data sets are contributed.”¹⁷

- [other repositories]

“A page of gene expression resources for Arachis: microarray and high throughput sequencing data sets at NCBI GEO, Array Express and Seq Read Archive (SRA)”¹⁸

16 <https://v1.legumefederation.org/data/v2/>

17 <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-63067-038-2.00008-3>

18 <https://peanutbase.org/external>

Inorganic Crystal Structure Database (ICSD)

Overview

ICSD is a disciplinary repository (chemistry) which has existed for a long time. Since it is subject to licensing, the databaseAccessType is restricted. The size field is filled with many generic and disciplinary units (size_unit_discipline) as well as with neutral and other information regarding the content (size_unit_content). Additionally, non-size information (size_non_unit_type) is integrated that offers error potential. No other technologies are known (softwareName, API, pidSystem). ICSDs record is over 10 years old and kept up-to-date (2022-04-28).

re3data.orgIdentifier	r3d100010085
repositoryName	Inorganic Crystal Structure Database
repositoryURL	https://icsd.fiz-karlsruhe.de/index.xhtml
repositoryIdentifier	FAIRsharing_doi:10.25504/FAIRsharing.a95199 biobdcore-001709
description	<p>The most comprehensive database on fully determined inorganic crystal structures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Full structural data: cell parameters, atom positions for all entries, displacement parameters• Full bibliographic data: publication title, journal reference(s), author names• Full structure description: Structural formula, compositions, ANX formulae, structure types• High-quality data: extensive data evaluation and correction by senior experts• Web and PC based software solutions, data updated twice a year• 25+ years of serving the scientific community
type	disciplinary
size	More than 262.000 entries, including >30.000 metal-organic structures, >23.000 theoretical structures. More than 235.000 structures are fully determined, around 12.000 structures are added each year. 3.100 crystal structures of the elements, 45.000 records for binary compounds, 83.000 records for ternary compounds, 96.000 records for quaternary and quinary compounds. >44.000 metals and around 12.000 minerals are included. About 185.000 entries (70%) have been assigned a structure type. There are currently 9,8003 structure prototypes. Detailed information can be found here https://icsd.products.fiz-karlsruhe.de/en/about/about-icsd
size_number	262000 30000 23000 235000 12000 3100 45000 83000 96000 44000 12000 185000 8003
size_unit	entries metal-organic structures theoretical structures structures are fully determined structures are added each year crystal structures of the elements records for binary compounds records for ternary compounds records for quaternary and quinary compounds metals minerals entries structure prototypes
size_unit_type	quantity

size_unit_discipline	generic disciplinary
size_unit_content	neutral other
size_non_unit_type	accuracy partof detail
size_quality	syntax error dot error
updated	2022-04-28
updated_corrected	28.04.2022
updated_quality	
startDate	1998
endDate	
repositoryLanguage	eng
subjects	3 Natural Sciences 31 Chemistry 316 Geochemistry, Mineralogy and Crystallography 32 Physics 34 Geosciences (including Geography) 4 Engineering Sciences 43 Materials Science and Engineering
contentType	Archived data Scientific and statistical data formats Structured graphics Structured text
providerType	dataProvider
keyword	cell chemistry crystal chemistry inorganic crystal structure intermetallic compounds
databaseAccessType	restricted
dataUploadType	restricted
softwareName	
api	
apiType	
pidSystem	
enhancedPublication	
certificate	
metadataStandardName	
remarks	Most of the structures contained in ICSD are published in journals, only a few entries were submitted as private communications. If you are a registered user of the ICSD database (Inorganic Crystal Structure Database), you will also find the deposited inorganic crystal structure data sets from 'Crystal Structure Depot' = r3d100010237 in this database, with a short production-dependent delay. The records in ICSD are produced from the original publication and the deposited data and have the advantage of having undergone additional checking.
entryDate	10.09.2012
lastUpdate	02.05.2022

Date of Retrieval

19.12.2022

GUI

Landing page

- [NA]

The screenshot shows the ICS D landing page with the following elements:

- Navigation:** A sidebar menu with options like 'Basic search & retrieve', 'Advanced search & retrieve', 'Bibliography', 'Cell', 'Chemistry', 'Symmetry', 'Crystal Chemistry', 'Structure Type', 'Experimental Information', 'DB Info', 'Expert Search', 'Query Management', 'Manage Queries', 'List Combined Queries', 'Create Combined Query', 'ICSD links', and 'ICSD News'.
- New Features:** A list of updates including the display of CCDC numbers, PDF export for powder patterns, improved mineral name search, links to the Open Quantum Materials Database (OQMD), and the inclusion of ORCID IDs.
- Key Features:** A list of search capabilities such as enhanced search functionality, extended information, easy analysis of large data sets, simple query management, personalization, visualization of powder patterns, content selection, and inclusion of abstracts.
- Visuals:** A 3D ball-and-stick model of a crystal structure within a unit cell, with bond lengths of 3.85 Å and 3.78 Å indicated. To the right, there are two XRD patterns for comparison.
- Header:** 'Welcome to ICSD Web.' and 'FIZ Karlsruhe | Contact'.
- Footer:** 'Legal Notices | Privacy Policy | Browser Recommendations | ©2022 FIZ Karlsruhe GmbH', 'Version 4.9.0 (build 20221026-1131) - Data Release 2022.2', and a build number.

Firefox_Screenshot_2022-12-19T17-10-10.299Z.png

Empty search

- [NA]
- [licensed access]

The screenshot shows the ICS D search interface with the following elements:

- Search Interface:** A 'Basic Search & Retrieve' section with a 'Free Text Search' input field and a 'Bibliography' section with fields for 'Authors', 'Year of Publication', 'Title of Journal', 'Title of Article', and 'DOI'.
- Notification:** A blue message box at the top right stating 'No results found for the given search criteria!' with 'Run Query' and 'Clear Query' buttons.
- Search Summary:** A section showing 'Basic Search: -'.
- Query History:** A section showing 'Number of queries: 0' and a 'Clear Query History' button.
- Header:** 'Welcome to ICSD Web. IP authenticated (141.52.248.4). Karlsruher Inst fuer Technologie'.
- Footer:** 'Login', 'Password', 'Login Personalized', 'Lost password?', 'Personalize account', and 'Content Selection' (with checkboxes for 'Experim. inorganic structures', 'Experim. metal-organic str.', and 'Theoretical structures').

Firefox_Screenshot_2022-12-19T17-35-37.499Z.png

- [Old site 2016]

“At present, the ICSD contains more than 187,000 entries, including

2,033 crystal structures of the elements

34,785 records for binary compounds

68,730 records for ternary compounds

68,083 records for quarternary and quinary compounds

About 149,000 entries (80%) have been assigned a structure type.

There are currently 9,093 structure prototypes.”¹⁹

Other sites

- “Around 12,000 new structures are added every year.

...

80 % of the structures are allocated to about 9,000 structure types. This allows for searches for substance classes.”²⁰

- “The ICSD database now contains 272,260 crystal structures.

During the update procedure, 10,059 new entries were added, 779 entries were modified and 41 entries were removed. The work on structure types has been expanded to the newly added and modified data. About 180,000 ICSD entries have now been assigned to 10,274 distinct structure types.”²¹

- [picture]

Firefox_Screenshot_2022-12-19T17-10-10.299Z_ICSD-Numbers.png

¹⁹ <https://web.archive.org/web/20161130230418/https://icsd.fiz-karlsruhe.de/search/index.xhtml?jsessionid=E65C55FB90D8287C32EAD23DA3B87D2D>

²⁰ <https://icsd.products.fiz-karlsruhe.de/>

²¹ <https://www.fiz-karlsruhe.de/en/produkte-und-dienstleistungen/inorganic-crystal-structure-database-icsd-news>

- [other units]

“We continuously extract and abstract the original data from over 80 leading scientific journals and more than 1,400 other scientific journals.”²²

- “Figures

Current Release: 2022.2

Entries:	272,260
Metal-organic structures:	35,174
Theoretical structures:	24,656
Derived Coordinates:	26,772
Fully determined:	245,488
New entries:	10,059
Modified entries:	779
Removed entries:	41
Structure Types:	10,274
Assigned to Structure Type:	191,132
Elements:	3,199
Binaries:	46,216
Ternaries:	85,045
Quaternaries:	60,334
Quintenaries:	40,133
Metals/Alloys:	45,609
Minerals:	12,121
Largest Structure:	2,122,042.75 Å ³
Smallest Structure:	10.51 Å ³
Authors:	130,814
Articles:	100,253
Journals:	1,676” ²³

²² <https://icsd.products.fiz-karlsruhe.de/en/about/about-icsd#general+information>

²³ <https://icsd.products.fiz-karlsruhe.de/en/about/about-icsd#facts+%26+figures>

API

- [not indexed in re3data]²⁴

Other Sources

- [outdated information from information brochure]²⁵
- [outdated information from publication]²⁶

Internal

- [last change request]

<r3d:size updated="202211-04 12:28">More than 262.181.000 entries, including >30.000 metal-organic structures, >23.000 theoretical structures. More than 235.000 structures are fully determined, around 12.000 structures are added each year. 3.100.033 crystal structures of the elements, 45.000.34.788 records for binary compounds, 83.000.68.730 records for ternary compounds, 96.000.68.083 records for quaternary and quinary compounds. >44.000 metals and around 12.000 minerals are included. About 185.49.000 entries (78,0%) have been assigned a structure type. There are currently 9.800.3 structure prototypes. Detailed information can be found here <https://icsd.products.fiz-karlsruhe.de/en/about/about-icsd/></r3d:size>

Firefox_Screenshot_2022-12-19T17-41-37.621Z.png

- [remarksIntern]

"T3730; Links geprüft 24.01.17(as); links corr. (es); #isIndexed; #isReviewed; Link corr; PCGC: ...www.fiz-karlsruhe.de/fiz_pgc.html start date ...www.fiz-karlsruhe.de/fileadmin/be_user/ICSD/PDF/sci_man_ICSD_v1.pdf Seiten nicht mehr vorhanden"

- [suggested contact]

"...@fiz-karlsruhe.de"

²⁴ <https://icsd.products.fiz-karlsruhe.de/en/products/icsd-products#icsd+api+service>

²⁵ <https://icsd.products.fiz-karlsruhe.de/sites/default/files/ICSD/documents/brochures/A-Focus-on-Crystallography.pdf>

²⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1107/S160057671900997X>

ScienceDB

Overview

ScienceDB is a generic repository with national scope (type: other) that provides more languages than English: Chinese. It has a filled size value with quantity and volume information, both generic regarding discipline and neutral regarding content and the content types are diversified. DOI is used as the pidSystem, specifically DataCite DOIs. It was recorded not recently (2019), with the entry not updated since the end of 2021.

re3data.orgIdentifier	r3d100013177
repositoryName	ScienceDB
repositoryURL	https://www.scidb.cn/en
repositoryIdentifier	FAIRsharing_doi:10.25504/fairsharing.tb0bkn doi:10.11922/sciencedb.0
description	Science Data Bank is an open generalist data repository developed and maintained by the Chinese Academy of Sciences Computing and Network Information Center (CNIC). It promotes the publication and reuse of scientific data. Researchers and journal publishers can use it to store, manage and share science data.
type	other
size	34.002 GB data; 488.533 datasets
size_number	34002 488533
size_unit	GB data datasets
size_unit_type	quantity volume
size_unit_discipline	generic
size_unit_content	neutral
size_non_unit_type	
size_quality	number error
updated	2021-08-04
updated_corrected	04.08.2021
updated_quality	
startDate	2015
endDate	
repositoryLanguage	eng zho
subjects	1 Humanities and Social Sciences 2 Life Sciences 3 Natural Sciences 4 Engineering Sciences

contentType	Archived data Audiovisual data Databases Images Networkbased data Plain text Raw data Scientific and statistical data formats Standard office documents Structured graphics Structured text
providerType	dataProvider
keyword	general purpose multidisciplinary
databaseAccessType	open
dataUploadType	restricted
softwareName	
api	
apiType	
pidSystem	DOI
enhancedPublication	yes
certificate	
metadataStandardName	Dublin Core
remarks	is covered by Elsevier.
entryDate	20.11.2019
lastUpdate	03.09.2021

Date of Retrieval

19.12.2022

GUI

Landing page

“6,682,294	“6,682,294
Open datasets	公开数据集
6,814,785	6,814,785
Deposited datasets	存储数据集
299,158 +GB	299,158 +GB
Data volume	数据体量
46,517,882	46,518,203
Page views	平台访问量
17,716,969	17,718,756
File downloads”	文件下载量”

27

- [Old site 2020]²⁸

Firefox_Screenshot_2022-12-20T17-49-18.477Z.png

²⁷ for chinese version change on the top right

²⁸ <https://web.archive.org/web/20200804014622/http://www.scidb.cn/en>

Empty search

- “6,682,294 results” “6,682,294 条结果”

Type	文件类型
<input type="checkbox"/> others (4,251,723)	<input type="checkbox"/> 其他 (4,251,723)
<input type="checkbox"/> dataset (398,360)	<input type="checkbox"/> 数据集/文件集 (398,360)
<input type="checkbox"/> figure or table in publications (282,269)	<input type="checkbox"/> 论文图表 (282,269)
<input type="checkbox"/> slide (42,038)	<input type="checkbox"/> 幻灯片 (42,038)
<input type="checkbox"/> code data (36,509)	<input type="checkbox"/> 代码数据 (36,509)
<input type="checkbox"/> multimedia data (3,263)	<input type="checkbox"/> 多媒体数据 (3,263)
Firefox_Screenshot_2022-12-20T17-53-22.772Z.png	Firefox_Screenshot_2022-12-20T18-11-40.950Z.png

29

Other sites

- [FAQ]³⁰

“At ScienceDB, we welcome submissions of data in any format, subject, or size.

ScienceDB对您提交的数据文件格式、内容涉及学科及数据文件大小没有强制限制”

API

- [not indexed in re3data]

“totalElements: 3921”³¹

- [OAI]

“completeListSize: 3921”³²

²⁹ <https://www.scidb.cn/en/list?searchList> for chinese version change on the top right

³⁰ <https://www.scidb.cn/en/faq#item2> for chinese version change on the top right

³¹ <https://www.scidb.cn/api/sdb-openapi-service/search> or https://www.scidb.cn/api/sdb-openapi-service/harvest?end_time=2099-01-01&page=1&size=10&start_time=1970-01-01

³² https://www.scidb.cn/oai?verb=ListRecords&metadataPrefix=oai_dc

Other Sources

- [publication 2017]

“Allow large-size (e.g., 1000GB) dataset to be uploaded and stored.”; “As of June 2017, 96 datasets were submitted into ScienceDB and among them 70 ones were published to allow open access.”³³

- [DataCite]

“Dataset 3,927”³⁴

Internal

- [last change request]

<r3d:size updated="2021-08-04">34,002 GB data; 488,533 datasets19-11-25">264 published datasets, 589 save datasets, 652 GB data</r3d:size>¶

Firefox_Screenshot_2022-12-20T18-43-51.657Z.png

- [remarksIntern]

“T3096: size~, mission~, policy+; editor: link check, -api; T2102; parallel URL: <http://www.sciencedb.cn/index>”

- [suggested contact:]

“...@cnic.cn “

³³ <https://dx.doi.org/10.1109/eScience.2017.38>

³⁴ <https://commons.datacite.org/doi.org?query=client.uid:cnic.sciencedb> or <https://api.datacite.org/does?client-id=cnic.sciencedb>

Appendix B
Datenmanagementplan (DMP)
für die DDM Masterarbeit

Titel der Arbeit: Does size matter?

Quality assessment of the size property in research data repositories

Name: Rouven Schabinger

Matrikelnummer: 20112

Datum Einreichung: 25.02.2023

Gliederung:

1. Allgemein	1
2. Inhaltliche Einordnung.....	2
3. Technische Einordnung.....	3
4. Datennutzung	5
5. Metadaten und Referenzierung.....	7
6. Rechtliche und ethische Fragen.....	7
7. Speicherung und Langzeitarchivierung.....	9

1. Allgemein

1.1 Thema

1.1.1. Wie lautet die primäre Forschungsfrage der Abschlussarbeit?

- Q1: For what semantic concepts is the size property of repositories being used?
- Q2: What kind of quality factors can be detected when assessing the size property in a registry for research data repositories (re3data)?
- Q3: Which automated (Q3.1) and intellectual (Q3.2) measures can improve the quality of the size property?

1.1.2. Bitte geben Sie einige Schlagwörter zur Forschungsfrage bzw. Fragestellung an.

Repository <Informatik>, GND:4303846-3

Größe, GND:4258353-6

Katalogisierung, GND:4163418-4

Qualitätssicherung, GND:4126457-5

Metadaten, GND:4410512-5

DDC: 005.74

DDC: 025.3

re3data, frei

1.1.3. Welchen Regeln oder Richtlinien (FHP, HUB) zum Umgang mit den in der Abschlussarbeit erhobenen Forschungsdaten folgen Sie für den DMP? Bitte referenzieren Sie diese hier inklusive Version bzw. Veröffentlichungsjahr.

Für die in der Arbeit erhobenen Forschungsdaten orientiert sich der Ersteller an der Forschungsdaten-Policy der Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin vom 8. Juli 2014¹, sowie den Handlungsempfehlungen in Ergänzung zu den Grundsätzen zum Umgang mit Forschungsdaten an der Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin² und der Forschungsdaten-Leitlinie der Fachhochschule Potsdam vom 4. November 2021³. Die Leitlinien der Fachhochschule Potsdam sehen einen Datenmanagementplan vor, der den Umgang mit den in der Arbeit erhobenen Daten beschreibt. Der Datenmanagementplan soll die Dokumentation, Speicherung, Archivierung, Veröffentlichung, Qualitätssicherung der Daten sowie Datenschutz und ethische Aspekte umfassen. Die Richtlinien beider Hochschulen stellen die

¹ <https://www.cms.hu-berlin.de/de/dl/dataman/infos/policy/grundsaeetze>

² <https://www.cms.hu-berlin.de/de/dl/dataman/infos/policy/guidelines/guidelines>

³ <https://www.fh-potsdam.de/sites/default/files/2021-12/421-forschungsdaten-policy-abk-fhpotsdam-21-11-04.pdf>

Nachvollziehbarkeit der Forschung in den Mittelpunkt, welche der Ersteller im Datenmanagementplan bezogen auf die hier beschriebenen Punkte berücksichtigt.

2. Inhaltliche Einordnung

2.1 Datensatz

2.1.1 Um welche Arten von Daten handelt es sich? Bitte in wenigen Zeilen kurz beschreiben.

Forschungsdaten-Repositoryn werden in re3data (registry of research data repositories) in der Regel über ein Antragsformular unter Angabe des Namens und der URL sowie weiterer Eigenschaften zur Aufnahme bei re3data vorgeschlagen. Ein Team prüft die Repositoryn anhand eines festgelegten Prüfschemas. Ein neuer Datensatz wird veröffentlicht, wenn die Mindestanforderungen der re3data-Policy erfüllt sind und die gesammelten Informationen von einem zweiten Teammitglied überprüft wurden. Siehe dazu "re3data registration workflow" in den FAQs⁴.

- Beim ersten Datensatz handelt es sich um vier Version tabellarischer Daten aus re3data. Hierbei wurden einige Metadaten aus dem Schema 2.2⁵ ausgewählt und über eine API heruntergeladen. Der Code sind Jupyter Notebooks in R, welche die Daten extrahieren, normalisieren und analysieren.
- Der zweite Datensatz enthält Text und Screenshots in Form einer Case Study (Thesis Appendix) von einzelnen Repositoryn-Webseiten und soll Indexierungsprobleme verdeutlichen.

2.2 Datenursprung

2.2.1 Werden die Daten selbst erzeugt oder nachgenutzt?

- Der erste Datensatz besteht hauptsächlich aus nachgenutzten Daten von re3data, die zum Teil weiterverarbeitet werden. Der Code wurde größtenteils selbst erzeugt, die API-Extraktion basiert auf einem im re3data COREF entwickelten Jupyter Notebook.
- Der zweite Datensatz wird auf Grundlage von Quelldokumenten selbst erzeugt.

2.2.2 Wenn die Daten nachgenutzt werden, wer hat die Daten erzeugt? Bitte mit Angabe des Identifiers, falls vorhanden, z.B. DOI.

Die Daten liegen in dem Verzeichnis re3data⁶ vor und können über eine API⁷ entsprechend heruntergeladen werden. Der vorliegende erste Datensatz wurde aber selbst

⁴ <https://www.re3data.org/faq>

⁵ <http://doi.org/10.48440/re3.010>

⁶ <https://www.re3data.org/>

⁷ <https://www.re3data.org/api/doc>

zusammengestellt und besteht nur aus einer Auswahl von Attributen. Der generische Code zur API von re3data ist hier zu finden.⁸

2.3. Reproduzierbarkeit

2.3.1 Sind die Daten reproduzierbar, d. h. ließen sie sich, wenn sie verloren gingen, erneut erstellen oder erheben?

Die Reproduzierbarkeit ist nur bedingt gegeben. Ausschlaggebend dafür ist der Zeitpunkt der Datenabfrage. Eine erneute Datenabfrage zu einem späteren Zeitpunkt wird wahrscheinlich nicht genau zu denselben Ergebnissen führen. Selbst bei Einschränkung des Zeitraums können die Felder der existenten Daten bei re3data aktualisiert worden sein. Hierfür müsste eine Versionierung vorliegen. Ggf. könnte man sich mit großem Aufwand aus re3data-internen Sicherung der Datenbank oder Datenabzügen bei anderen Providern wie DataCite mit Hilfe von Update-Feldern dem Originalzustand der Daten annähern. Der zweite Datensatz ist auch stark vom Zeitpunkt abhängig, hier könnte man sich evtl. mit Hilfe der WaybackMachine dem Zustand der Repositorien-Webseite annähern.

Aus den extrahierten Daten lassen sich die automatischen Schritte über den Code nachvollziehen. Die intellektuelle Typisierung und Feinkorrektur der Daten ist höchstwahrscheinlich nicht komplett reproduzierbar. Die verwendete Vorgehensweise ist aber im Methodik-Kapitel der Thesis dokumentiert.

2.4 Nachnutzung

2.4 Für welche Personen, Gruppen oder Institutionen könnte dieser Datensatz (für die Nachnutzung) von Interesse sein? Für welche Szenarien ist dies denkbar?

Die Datensätze sind für Infrastrukturanbieter aus dem Forschungsdatenmanagement interessant. Auch für benachbarte Bereiche wie Katalogisierende aus dem Bibliothekswesen könnte sie Informationen bieten.

3. Technische Einordnung

3.1 Datenerhebung

3.1.1 Wann erfolgt(e) die Erhebung bzw. Erstellung der Daten?

- Der Abruf der Daten aus re3data erfolgte am 26.11.2022; Der Code wurde begleitend vom November 2022 bis Januar 2023 kreiert.
- Die Roherfassung des zweiten Datensatzes zwischen 17. und 20.12.2022

3.1.2 Wann erfolgt(e) die Datenbereinigung / -aufbereitung bzw. Datenanalyse?

⁸ https://github.com/re3data/using_the_re3data_API

Die Datenbereinigung und -aufbereitung erfolgte im Dezember 2022. Die Datenanalyse begann im selben Monat und endete im Januar 2023.

3.1 Datengröße

3.1.1 Was ist die tatsächliche oder erwartete Größe der Daten(typen)?

Die Größe der Daten beträgt weniger als 1 GB.

3.2 Formate

3.2.1 In welchen Formaten liegen die Daten vor?

- Die abgerufenen Daten des ersten Datensatzes liegen größtenteils als CSVs oder XLSX vor. Der Code ist als IPYNB in R abgelegt.
- Beim zweiten Datensatz handelt es sich um Text in DOCX/PDF mit integrierten Screenshots ursprünglich in PNG-Format.

3.3 Werkzeuge

3.3.1 Welche Instrumente, Software, Technologien oder Verfahren werden zur Erzeugung, Erfassung, Bereinigung, Analyse und/oder Visualisierung der Daten genutzt? Bitte (falls möglich) mit Versionsnummer und Referenz in Form einer Adresse jeweils angeben.

Der Abruf der Daten erfolgte über eine API bei re3data mithilfe eines R-Skriptes (R 4.0.2), ausgeführt in einem Jupyter Notebook (Jupyterlab Version 3.2.1) in der HDF-Cloud (Helmholtz Data Federation) vom Jülich Supercomputing Centre (JSC) des Forschungszentrums Jülich⁹. Dort folgte auch die Bereinigung der Daten und die Auswertung und Visualisierung. Lediglich die intellektuelle Bearbeitung erfolgte in Microsoft Excel 2016. Text- und Bilderfassung der Case Study erfolgte via Mozilla Firefox (102.7.0 esr - 64-bit) und Easyscreenshot (Version 3.91).

3.3.2 Welche Software, Verfahren oder Technologien sind notwendig, um die Daten zu nutzen?

Um die prozessierten Daten zu nutzen, ist die Verwendung eine CSV verarbeitenden Programms nötig, für die XLSX Microsoft Excel. Der Code benötigt ein Jupyter Notebook. Das Dokument (PDF) im Appendix kann z.B. mit Adobe Reader geöffnet

⁹ <https://jupyter-jsc.fz-juelich.de>

3.4 Versionierung

3.4.1 Werden verschiedene Versionen der Daten erzeugt (z. B. durch verschiedene Weiterverarbeitungsprozesse bzw. Bereinigung von Daten)?

Es wurden verschiedene Versionen der Daten des ersten Datensatzes erzeugt, jeweils bei den erfolgten Verarbeitungsschritten:

- Version 1: Abgerufene Daten über die API
- Version 2: Bereinigte Daten
- Version 3: Typisierte Daten
- Version 4: Detaillierte Typisierung für einen Teil der Daten auf Unit- und nicht mehr auf Repositoriumslevel¹⁰

4. Datennutzung

4.1 Datenorganisation

4.1.1 Gibt es eine Strategie zur Benennung der Daten? Wenn ja, bitte skizzieren Sie sie kurz.

Die Daten sind in die oben genannten zwei Datensätze und den Code aufgeteilt:

- Dataset re3data und Code
- Case Study im Appendix

Beim Vorliegen mehrerer Versionen einer Datei im jeweiligen Bearbeitungsschritt, wurden diese durch eine Versionsangabe im Dateinamen eindeutig benannt. Die Dateien wurden durch Hochzählen der Zahl bei der Versionsangabe, z. B. v2, versioniert.

repository_info_v1.csv

4.2 Datenspeicherung und -sicherheit

4.2.1 Wer darf (zukünftig) auf die Daten zugreifen?

Die Daten werden für alle über Zenodo in der DDM Community zur Verfügung gestellt.¹¹

4.2.2 Wie und wie oft werden Backups der Daten erstellt?

Neben den lokalen Kopien der Daten auf dem Rechner des Erstellers wurde eine Kopie der Daten auf dem zentralen Netzlaufwerk der KIT-Bibliothek gespeichert, das regelmäßig

¹⁰ Details sind in der documentation.txt angegeben

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/ddm>

gebackupt wurde. Eine weitere Kopie wurde auf GoogleDrive gesichert. Nach jeder zentralen Änderung oder mindestens einmal am Tag (bei Veränderung) erfolgte ein Abzug.

4.3 Interoperabilität

4.3.1 Sind die Datenformate im Sinne der FAIR-Prinzipien interoperabel, d.h. geeignet für den Datenaustausch und die Nachnutzung zwischen bzw. von unterschiedlichen Forschenden, Institutionen, Organisationen und Ländern?

- Für die Daten wurden standardisierte Formate genutzt: CSV-Format, XLSX-Format, R/Jupyter, PNG/PDF.
- Sie sind mit (offener) Software bzw. mit in der jeweiligen Community etablierter und viel genutzter Software nutzbar: Texteditoren, Excel und Jupyter.
- Die Daten können ohne großen Aufwand mit verschiedenen anderen Datensätzen aus unterschiedlichen Quellen kombiniert werden.

4.4 Weitergabe und Veröffentlichung

4.4.1 Ist es geplant, die Daten nach Abgabe der Abschlussarbeit zu veröffentlichen oder zu teilen?

Die Daten werden für alle über Zenodo in der DDM Community zur Verfügung gestellt.¹²

4.4.2 Wenn nicht, skizzieren Sie kurz rechtliche und/oder vertragliche Gründe und freiwillige Einschränkungen.

Trifft nicht zu.

4.4.3 Wenn ja, unter welchen Nutzungsbedingungen oder welcher Lizenz sollen die Daten veröffentlicht bzw. geteilt werden?

Die Daten sollen unter der Lizenz CC0 zur Verfügung gestellt werden. Die Skripte stehen unter einer MIT License.

4.5 Qualitätssicherung

4.5.1 Welche Maßnahmen zur Qualitätssicherung (z. B. Plausibilitätsprüfung von Datenwerten) werden für die Daten ergriffen?

Eine Maßnahme der Qualitätssicherung war die Korrektur von Schreibfehlern in den Daten. Bei größeren Unsicherheiten bezüglich der abgerufenen Daten erfolgte eine Plausibilitätsprüfung der Daten durch Abgleich mit dem Display der Web-Oberfläche von

¹² <https://zenodo.org/communities/ddm>

re3data oder internen Checks. Ein dezidiertes Review der Daten durch weitere Personen war bei der Thesis nicht vorgesehen.

4.6 Datenintegration

4.6.1 Falls Daten aus verschiedenen Quellen (z. B. Anpassung Skalierung, Zeiträume, Ortsangaben) integriert werden, wie wird dies gewährleistet?

Trifft nicht zu.

5. Metadaten und Referenzierung

5.1 Metadaten

5.1.1 Welche Informationen sind für Außenstehende notwendig, um die Daten zu verstehen (d. h. ihre Erhebung bzw. Entstehung, Analyse sowie die auf ihrer Basis gewonnenen Forschungsergebnisse nachvollziehen) und nachnutzen zu können?

Notwendige Informationen:

- (Ort)
- Zeit
- Erzeugungsprozess
- Methodik
- Inhalt
- Technologie
- Quellen

5.1.2 Welche Standards, Ontologien, Klassifikationen etc. werden zur Beschreibung der Daten und Kontextinformation genutzt?

Die Daten sind bereits durch re3data beschrieben. Die Beschreibung basiert auf einem eigenen Standard von re3data, der auf anderen Standards, wie z. B. ISO-8601; <http://www.w3.org/TR/NOTE-datetime>, verweist. Darüber hinaus wird kein festgelegtes System zur Beschreibung genutzt.

6. Rechtliche und ethische Fragen

6.1 Personenbezogene Daten

6.1.1 Enthalten die Daten personenbezogene Informationen?

Trifft nicht zu.

6.2 Sensible Daten

6.2.1 Enthalten die Daten "Angaben über die rassische und ethnische Herkunft, politische Meinungen, religiöse oder philosophische Überzeugungen, Gewerkschaftszugehörigkeit, Gesundheit oder Sexualleben" (BDSG §3, Abs.9)?

Trifft nicht zu.

6.2.2 Werden die Daten anonymisiert oder pseudonymisiert?

Trifft nicht zu.

6.2.3 Haben Sie eine "informierte Einwilligung" der Betroffenen eingeholt? Fügen Sie bitte ein Template der Einverständniserklärung als Anlage bei.

Trifft nicht zu.

6.2.4 Wenn keine "informierte Einwilligung" eingeholt wird, begründen Sie dies bitte.

Trifft nicht zu.

6.2.5 Wo und wie sind die "informierten Einwilligungen" abgelegt?

Trifft nicht zu.

6.2.6 Bis wann werden die (unanonymisierten bzw. unpseudonymisierten) Originaldaten spätestens sicher vernichtet?

Trifft nicht zu.

6.3 Urheber- oder verwandte Schutzrechte

6.3.1 Werden Daten genutzt und/oder erstellt, die durch Urheber- oder verwandte Schutzrechte geschützt sind?

Die Codebasis für re3data_extract ist im Rahmen der re3ata COREF Projekts entstanden.
Die Screenshots bewegen sich im Rahmen des (Bild-)Zitatrechts.

7. Speicherung und Langzeitarchivierung

7.1 Wo werden die Daten (einschließlich Metadaten, Dokumentation und ggf. relevantem Code bzw. relevanter Software) während Phase der Erarbeitung der Abschlussarbeit gespeichert?

Die Daten werden lokal auf dem Rechner des Erstellers, dem Netzlaufwerk der KIT-Bibliothek und GoogleDrive gespeichert.

7.2 Wo werden die Daten (einschließlich Metadaten, Dokumentation und ggf. relevantem Code bzw. relevanter Software) nach dem Ende der Abschlussarbeit gespeichert bzw. archiviert?

Die Daten werden über Zenodo veröffentlicht.¹³

7.3 Handelt es sich dabei um ein zertifiziertes Repositorium oder Datenzentrum (z.B. durch das CoreTrustSeal, nestor-Siegel oder ISO 16363)? (Wurden mehrere Langzeitarchivierungsoptionen ausgewählt, kann die Frage bejaht werden, wenn dies auf mindestens eine der Optionen zutrifft).

Zenodo ist nicht zertifiziert, unternimmt aber Schritte zur Langzeitarchivierung¹⁴ und wird im Rahmen des Studiengangs im Rahmen dessen die Masterarbeitsdaten entstanden für die entsprechende DDM Community empfohlen.

¹³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/ddm>

¹⁴ <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

C Overview over Research Data and Code

re3data_analysis.ipynb

re3data_extract.ipynb

re3data_normalize.ipynb

repository_info_v1.csv

repository_info_v2.csv

repository_info_v3.csv

repository_info_v3.xlsx

repository_info_v4.csv

documentation.txt

Data availability

The code and data from the analysis of re3data is published at Zenodo under the following DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7643637>.